

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
California State University, Los Angeles

EVALUATING PROVIDER PERCEIVED IMPROVED HEPATITIS-C
MANAGEMENT SKILLS AFTER HYBRID SCAN-ECHO
EDUCATIONAL SERIES

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

Esther Memrero Robinson

Doctoral Project Committee Approval:

Elizabeth J. Winokur, Ph.D., RN, CEN, Project Lead
Ayman K. Tailakh, Ph.D., RN, Project Co-Lead

May 2019

Copyright Esther Memrero Robinson 2019 ©

ABSTRACT

Hepatitis-C is a viral infection leading to chronic liver inflammation or cirrhosis that can be potentially fatal. However, the disease is treatable, and it is thus alarming that this highly manageable and treatable disease continues to needlessly end lives because those infected are often not readily screened, diagnosed, treated, and managed effectively. Although the segment of the population known as the birth cohort (those born between 1945-1965) are disproportionately impacted by Hepatitis-C (HCV), many are not readily screened, diagnosed, treated, and managed successfully over time.

Twenty-one primary care providers (PCPs) participated in a hybrid Specialty Care Access Network-Extension for Community Healthcare Outcomes (SCAN-ECHO) educational and management series starting in 2016. Subsequently, they were invited to complete an anonymous online survey via SurveyMonkey regarding their related perceptions of increased competency in the identification, screening, diagnosis, treatment and ongoing management of patients with Hepatitis-C. Ten (48%) PCPs completed the online survey.

Descriptive analysis showed that the vast majority (90%) felt that participation in the hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational series positively impacted the following: (1) confidence in knowledge about Hepatitis-C and chronic disease; (2) confidence in Hepatitis-C management skills; and (3) attitudes towards HCV patient care.

Exposing PCPs to experts such as through a hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational and management series can augment their knowledge and skills in the identification, screening, diagnosis, treatment and ongoing management of patients with Hepatitis-C. In turn, they will report overall positive attitudes about the importance of HCV patient care strategies and practices.

Keywords: Hepatitis-C, HCV, Primary Care Providers, Patients, Patient Care, Knowledge, Management Skills, Attitude, Confidence, Identification, Screening, Diagnosis, Treatment

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	iii
LIST OF TABLES.....	vii
LIST OF FIGURES	viii
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	ix
BACKGROUND	1
Problem Statement.....	1
Purpose Statement.....	4
Supporting Framework	5
REVIEW OF LITERATURE	12
Overview.....	12
Primary Care Provider Awareness of Hepatitis-C.....	13
Role in Hepatitis-C Management	14
Hepatitis-C Knowledge.....	15
Hepatitis-C Practice Patterns	16
Origins of ECHO	18
Evidence of ECHO Usage	19
Implementation of SCAN-ECHO within the VHA	20
Summary.....	21
METHODS	22
Setting.....	22
Sample	23
Procedures.....	23
Ethical Issues	25
Planning the Quality Improvement Program	26
Methods of Evaluation.....	26
RESULTS	30
DISCUSSION.....	41

Limitations	44
Recommendations.....	44
Implications	45
REFERENCES	47
APPENDIX A: RECRUITMENT E-MAIL	58
APPENDIX B: PROJECT SURVEY PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET	61
APPENDIX C: NUTCOMP Tool ADAPTATION REQUEST LETTER.....	62
APPENDIX D: HEP-C COMPETENCY TOOL	63
APPENDIX E: IRB APPROVAL LETTERS.....	66
APPENDIX F: TABLE OF EVIDENCE FOR PROJECT	69

LIST OF TABLES

<u>Table</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Descriptive Statistics Summary	32
2. Profession * Motivation for Participation Crosstabulation	39
3. Narrative Responses of Participation Impact.....	40
4. Table of Evidence Used for Project.....	69

LIST OF FIGURES

<u>Figure</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Supporting framework for DNP project	10
2. Supporting framework applied to data-gathering and analysis process	27
3. Confidence in knowledge about hepatitis-C and chronic disease.....	32
4. Confidence in hepatitis-C management skills	34
5. Attitudes towards HCV patient care	36
6. Motivation for participation.....	37

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I wholeheartedly wish to recognize all those who were instrumental in helping me complete this scholarly project especially the primary care providers who were the subject. I am very grateful for the time you took to complete the survey. I also wish to thank all those who supported me in one way or another on my journey to accomplishing my goal of obtaining this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) degree. I am especially forever grateful to Dr. Elizabeth Winokur (Project Team Leader) for believing in me and guiding me to this reality. I also wish to thank CSU Consortium faculty Ayman Tailakh (Project Co-Team Leader). Additionally, I thank Dr. Donna Scemons and Dr. Dana Rutledge for their feedback during the writing of the proposal for the project and my project champion at my organizational facility Dr. Debika Bhattacharya for all the supportive guidance and words of encouragement that made the completion of this DNP project a reality.

I wish to thank all my family (my mother, brothers – especially our recently departed eldest brother Samuel and sisters), friends, and colleagues for their love, support, and prayerful well-wishes during this academic journey. In one way or another without realizing it, you each gave me the courage and strength to see this journey through to its joyous conclusion. To my beloved husband, Isaiah, I am who I am today and who I will be tomorrow because of your amazing love, encouragement and unwavering support of my personal, educational and professional pursuits. Finally, to my

beloved dearly departed papa, I am forever grateful to you for instilling in me the love of life-long learning. I dedicate this DNP degree to you in ever-loving memory!

BACKGROUND

According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC, 2016), Hepatitis-C is a viral infection leading to chronic liver inflammation or cirrhosis that can be potentially fatal. The disease is caused by the Hepatitis-C virus (HCV). Sometimes, those newly infected do not present with symptoms of the disease, which may include jaundice that eventually resolves. Although fatigue, skin disorders, and other health complications may be present, those chronically infected are often asymptomatic and are thus not identified early leading to untimely deaths (CDC, 2016).

The incidence and prevalence of Hepatitis-C worldwide and in the United States (U.S.) have been well-documented. This severe disease has far-reaching effects as it causes countless untimely deaths. According to World Health Organization (WHO) data, there are at least 170-200 million people with HCV infection globally (WHO, 2017). Of those infected, within the first six months of exposure 15-45% will be rid of the virus without having had any medical treatment. Chronic HCV infection will develop in the rest (WHO, 2017). There is a 15-30% risk of cirrhosis of the liver within 20 years in those with chronic HCV infection (WHO, 2017). Chronic HCV infection is the principal basis for liver transplantation procedures in the U.S. (Dultz et al., 2017).

Problem Statement

Surveillance data released by CDC in 2016 revealed that deaths from the disease peaked at 19,659 in 2014 (CDC, 2016). Another CDC study showed that in 2013, Hepatitis C-associated deaths outnumbered the combined totals from the other 60 infectious diseases, which included tuberculosis, human immunodeficiency virus (HIV), and pneumococcal disease (CDC, 2016). Because both studies mentioned relied on data

gathered from death certificates known to underreport Hepatitis-C as a cause of death frequently, there is a high likelihood that the actual death totals were much higher than reported (CDC, 2016). Thus, it is alarming that this highly manageable and treatable disease continues to needlessly end lives because those infected are often not readily screened, diagnosed, treated, and managed effectively. The impact of global and U.S. prevalence rates has been well-documented.

Hepatitis-C Prevalence

Globally

Global estimates indicate that 2-3% of individuals are living with HCV infection with at least 399,000 dying yearly of HCV-related conditions such as cirrhosis and liver cancer (WHO, 2017). There are variations in the incidence, distribution, and control of the disease amongst the world's population with a range of < 1% to > 10% cited as country-specific prevalence rates (Averhoff, Glass, & Holtzman, 2012; WHO, 2017). Experts contend that multiple strains (or genotypes) of HCV exist and their distribution varies by country (WHO, 2017).

The WHO Eastern Mediterranean and European Regions have the highest prevalence rates of 2.3% and 1.5% respectively (WHO, 2017). Examination of country-specific data reveals that HCV infection is localized to specific populations (for example, injectable drug abusers or the homeless) versus the general populations (WHO, 2017). In the U.S., HCV infection distribution rates also vary.

United States

In the U.S., an estimated 3.2 million individuals are infected with HCV. Individuals born during 1945-1965 (known as the birth cohort) comprise approximately

75% of those infected. According to the U.S. Preventive Services Task Force (USPSTF), this cohort is up to five times more likely to be infected. Their risk is highest because of personal high-risk factors such as past or current intravenous (IV) drug use or history of blood transfusions before strict screening guidelines for donated blood were instituted in 1992. Hepatitis-C is a leading cause of liver cancer and the leading cause of liver transplants; with the birth-cohort accounting for 73% of all Hepatitis C-associated mortality (Chak, Talal, Sherman, Schiff, & Saab, 2011; Dultz et al., 2017; Moyer, 2013; USPSTF, 2012). Therefore, it is highly recommended that this group be targeted for screening, diagnosis, and treatment for the most positive impact on healthcare resources.

Rein et al. (2017), in their cost-effectiveness simulation study, determined that in primary care settings, birth-cohort screening for HCV was cost-effective. They identified 808,580 cases of chronic HCV infection with screening costs of \$2874 per case. The most extensive U.S. veteran population group belong to the birth-cohort sub-population so that their care and needs are of the highest priority. In the Veterans Health Administration (VHA), targeting this group, therefore, averts resource depletion if cases can be identified and treated promptly.

Veterans Health Administration Population Data and Results of One Local Study

In the U.S., there are approximately 250,000 homeless veterans receiving care within the VHA system, and approximately 13.4% of them have chronic HCV infection (Bakr et al., 2018). By contrast, only 3.5% of the 5,424,814 non-homeless veterans are infected with HCV with 31% of non-homeless veterans who are infected receiving antiviral therapy compared to only 22.9% of homeless veterans (Bakr et al., 2018). Thus,

at a local Southern California VHA healthcare system in 2016, efforts were directed at increasing access to care for HCV-infected homeless veterans.

Infectious disease specialists from the Liver Clinic and Primary Care Providers (PCPs) in the Homeless Patient-Aligned Care Team (HPACT) collaborated to pilot-test a combined telemedicine and in-person focused HCV treatment program for their homeless veterans (Bakr et al., 2018). The Specialty Care Access Network Extension for Community Healthcare Outcomes (SCAN-ECHO) educational series was the telemedicine component utilized. The program goal was to comprehend/describe the demographics of homeless veterans designated for treatment, viral response rates, and treatment completion rates (Bakr et al., 2018).

Twenty-one homeless veterans were deemed eligible from which ten were selected for participation based on a recommendation from PCPs of their history of adherence to the medical plan of care (POC) and thus good prospects of completing the HCV course of treatment (Bakr et al., 2018). The ten homeless veterans were male and 70% non-Hispanic Black with a mean age of 58.5 years; they were homeless or recently homeless with a history of polysubstance abuse (Bakr et al., 2018). The researchers concluded that study participants could self-identify others who were also able to complete the program despite a history of poly-substance abuse. Thus, they noted that the incorporation of the HCV treatment program into the pre-existing interdisciplinary, patient-centered medical home setting of the HPACT, created an environment for success as it actively engaged this group of patients who were previously otherwise unreachable (Bakr et al., 2018). To that end, the impact of PCPs in this endeavor cannot be overstated.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project, therefore, was to evaluate the impact of the 2016 hybrid Specialty Care Access Network-Extension for Community Healthcare Outcomes (SCAN-ECHO) educational and management series on perceptions by participating Primary Care Providers (PCPs) at a local VHA healthcare system of their increased competency in the identification, screening, diagnosis, treatment and ongoing management of patients with Hepatitis-C. The DNP project aimed at answering the following questions:

1. Did participation in the hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational and management series in 2016 result in perceived improved confidence in knowledge about Hepatitis-C and chronic disease?
2. Did participation in the hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational and management series in 2016 result in perceived improved confidence in Hepatitis-C management skills?
3. What are the attitudes of PCPs who participated in the hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational and management series in 2016 towards HCV patient care?
4. Will PCPs report that participation in the hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational and management series in 2016 resulted in improvement of their management of HCV types of patients?

Supporting Framework

Frameworks are the foundation on which research studies and quality improvement project initiatives emerge. Clinical practice and scientific research require an excellent framework (Zaccagnini & White, 2014). The framework that guided this

DNP project is the Logic Model (LM). “A logic model is a systematic and visual way to present and share your understanding of the relationships among the resources you have to operate your program, the activities you plan, and the changes or results you hope to achieve.” (W.K. Kellogg Foundation 2004, p. 1). The LM can be used for guiding program planning through to implementations and for subsequent evaluation of the extent of impact or success later.

The LM explains the interrelationship of these elements: inputs (invested resources) such as activities, outputs (program processes) including identification of who does what, and overall outcomes (short-term, intermediate, and long-term) affecting the service or program (Figure 1). Logic models are engrained within change theories and use words and/or pictures to illustrate the succession of actions and/or activities believed to generate change and how these actions and/or activities are connected to the overall effects the program is predicted to accomplish. The path aimed at discerning the journey through transformation includes: (1) pinpointing the problem(s); (2) designating desired results; and (3) developing the approach for reaching the goal(s).

Resources include such things as people, capital, or financial inducements, and stakeholders. Actions and/or activities include such things as recruitment and marketing, needs assessments, and program of study, et cetera needed to plan, implement, or evaluate a program. Outputs include byproducts resulting from the service or program, such as in the case of the 2016 pilot study that is the impetus for this DNP project, the number of patients served by the Homeless Patient-Aligned Care Team (HPACT) and the extent of the intervention. Short-term outcomes are such things as the extent of transformations in the participants’ knowledge, skills, or attitudes (KSA) as can be

confirmed by the administration of a survey. Intermediate outcomes are apparent behavioral transformations. Long-term outcomes deal with the overall impact or far-reaching effects of the service or program such as decreases in rates of HCV in the homeless veteran (HV) population as in the case of the 2016 pilot study that is the impetus for this DNP project.

Use of the Logic Model

Effective use of the LM underscores the dynamic nature of humanistic services and programs such as an outreach to patient care population and supports program improvement activities as time progresses (CDC, 2018; Isreal, 2010; Renger & Hurley, 2006; W. K. Kellogg Foundation, 2004). Stakeholder engagement at the start of program planning through to implementation illuminates program purposes from various perspectives. Stakeholders comprise the participants or program beneficiaries, service providers, administrative personnel overseeing the program, benefactors, and the population at-large. The LM has been used in various formats such as to demonstrate success in providing education about teen pregnancy and sexually transmitted infections (STI) or human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) prevention strategies (Fluhr, Oman, Allen, Lanphier, & McLeroy, 2004; Hulton, 2007).

Logic Model Applied to Hepatitis-C Programs and Services

Specifically, the LM has also been used in the development, implementation, and evaluation of programs and services targeting Hepatitis-C patients. Fathauer and Meek (2012) used the LM in their case report description of their efforts in designing, implementing, and initial evaluation of an HCV-specific clinical decision support system (CDSS) embedded within an electronic health record (EHR). A program LM was devised

to identify the inputs, outputs, and expected outcomes from the development and implementation of the CDSS.

The World Health Organization (WHO, 2016) in their technical report on the monitoring and evaluation for viral Hepatitis-B and Hepatitis-C proposed the use of the LM as the framework for undertaking this task. The LM was used to guide data collection and analysis for ten key indicators that included prevalence and incidence rates.

The Government of South Australia used the LM as the supporting framework for their development, implementation, and evaluation of a nursing model of care for viral Hepatitis management. The use of the LM enabled them to clearly define what types of services to provide, who the specific target population would be and what overall impact they hoped to reach. Thus, it is by the appeal of these LM three key features (inputs, outputs, & outcomes) showing the dynamics of how and why efficiently program change occurs that the framework was selected to guide this DNP final project.

Application of the Supporting Framework to the DNP Project

The Logic Model (LM) framework is appropriate for this project because it focuses on the inter-relationships among several dynamics. These are such things as the available resources, intended actions, and expected results in individual or group behavioral change in the context of an adult learning environment as with the use of the hybrid Specialty Care Access Network-Extension for Community Healthcare Outcomes (SCAN-ECHO) educational and management series program. The impetus for the use of the hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational and management series in the 2016 pilot study was the need for PCPs to augment their knowledge and competency in order to efficiently identify, screen, treat, and manage Hepatitis-C patients. The first step in using LM in the

current DNP project was to assess the setting in which the planned activity was to occur. Thus, the DNP student researcher sought input from various stakeholders; notably, the Associate Chief of the Infectious Diseases Department. She was supportive of evaluating the impact of the 2016 pilot study using the hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational and management series on PCP improved HCV patient management skills. However, there was a stipulation that any survey instrument(s) used could be no longer than 10-15 questions in length.

Inputs

The Veterans Administration Medical Center (VAMC) facility where the project was undertaken has the needed resources (i.e., computers) that were used by the DNP student researcher to send the recruitment e-mail to the PCPs. There were time commitments on the part of the DNP student researcher to draft and send the recruitment e-mail with participant information details to the PCPs. There were also time commitments on the parts of the PCPs to complete the online survey promptly.

Outputs

The DNP student researcher obtained the VAMC Institutional Review Board (IRB) and California State University, Los Angeles (CSULA) IRB approvals, which were granted (See Appendix E). The DNP student researcher then recruited PCPs via e-mail requesting that they complete the online survey promptly. The goal of the project was to effectively utilize resources and activities to achieve the goal of evaluating whether PCPs believe that participation in the 2016 pilot study using the hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational series improved their Hepatitis-C patient management skills. The aims were focused on investigating how the extent of the existence of reported perceived

improvements in PCP knowledge, competency, and attitude toward Hepatitis-C patient care increased their sense of self-actualization and sustained or increased screening of patients over time since the 2016 pilot study.

Outcomes

PCPs were expected to report significant improvements in their knowledge, competency, and attitudes toward Hepatitis-C patient care. Assumptions are that all PCPs would report having been highly satisfied with the impact of the use of the hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational series in the 2016 pilot study on their improved Hepatitis-C management skills. Overall, veteran health outcomes may be improved because of PCP improved management skills resulting in increased screening rates.

Inputs (What we invest)	Outputs (What we do and who we do it to)		Outcomes – Impact (The incremental events/changes that occur as a result of the outputs)		
	<i>Activities</i>	<i>Participation</i>	<i>Short</i>	<i>Medium</i>	<i>Long</i>
Time Computers VAMC facility DNP Student Researcher PCPs	PCP recruitment via e-mail to complete online survey Consent for participation & complete online survey Obtain VAMC IRB & CSULA IRB approvals Data retrievals & analysis	DNP Student Researcher PCPs DNP Student Researcher DNP Student Researcher/DNP Faculty Adviser/ Project Team Leader	PCPs are aware of the current QI project to complete the online survey & do so timely VAMC IRB & CSULA IRB approvals are obtained timely DNP Student Researcher/DNP Project Team Leader complete data retrievals and analysis timely	PCPs complete online survey promptly PCPs self-report improved HCV management skills	Improved HCV health outcomes for veterans because of PCP self-reported improved management skills as shown by increased screening rates. Improved ability of veterans to take part in all aspects of life through increased access to very prompt HCV screening services.
ASSUMPTIONS (root cause analyses, prior learning/experience) Participation in the 2016 pilot study using the SCAN-ECHO educational series did improve PCP Hep-C management skills. There has been an increase in HCV identification rates since the 2016 pilot study. Early identification has improved patient health outcomes; decreased mortality. The VAMC IRB & CSULA IRB will approve the project timely. PCPs will consent to and complete the online survey promptly.			EXTERNAL FACTORS (barriers/facilitators) VAMC server may cause e-mail issues, which will affect the ability of DNP student researcher to send recruitment e-mail to PCPs. VAMC server may cause e-mail issues, which will affect the ability of PCPs to complete the online survey promptly.		

Figure 1. Supporting framework for DNP project: Logic Model (LM)

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Overview

According to Zaccagnini and White (2014), a general review of the literature (ROL) is accomplished to develop an understanding of the nature and scope of the identified problem and to determine the extent of available related pre-existing research. The effectiveness of the use of the Extension for Community Healthcare Outcomes (ECHO) concept to expose PCPs to subject-matter experts in such areas as pain management, hypertension (HTN) management, and liver disease management is clearly evidenced (Scott et al., 2012; Moore & Manch, 2013; Katzman et al., 2014; Salgia, McCurdy, & Moseley, 2014). Thus, a ROL was conducted as a background for the development of this DNP project. The literature on the improvement of PCP Hepatitis-C competency is readily available. The electronic databases used included CINAHL, PubMed, ScienceDirect, PsycINFO, Google Scholar, and Academic Search Premier to look for evidence of publications relevant to the topics of augmenting PCP Hepatitis-C skills competency in general and within the VHA.

Databases were searched for articles primarily published between 2013 to 2018. In specific instances, the search timeframe was extended to as early as 2001 when a limited number of articles were retrieved. Supplemental sources utilized were journals in areas such as hepatology, family medicine, internal medicine, and telemedicine. MeSH terms that were used included PCP awareness of Hepatitis-C and its treatment and origins of the ECHO concepts and its use across healthcare settings and within the VHA. More search terms included prevalence and incidence of Hepatitis-C globally and in the U.S.,

treatment adherence, primary care provider HCV competency, continuing education, and the use of peer support groups to increase patient adherence to treatment.

The articles that were included contained primary source discussions from original research that were published in peer-reviewed journals and those published by suitable national and international professional and governmental agencies such as the CDC and the WHO. Peer-reviewed journal publications represented most of the articles selected for review. The reference lists of retrieved documents were further searched manually to identify relevant publications to narrow down the list finally. Exclusion criteria included duplications across databases, non-English and those articles that focused on experimental treatments. The initial search yielded 599 articles which were narrowed to 70 articles after accounting for duplicates and those that did not meet the inclusion criteria. The 70 selected articles were critically appraised for their content and to determine whether they added to the understanding of the problem under exploration which resulted in 61 articles. From these 61 articles, 50 were ultimately used for this DNP final project. The articles used included systematic reviews, cohort studies, qualitative studies, and consensus reports from governmental and professional agencies.

Primary Care Providers' Awareness of Hepatitis-C and its Treatment

PCPs are usually the first line group of healthcare professionals that patients encounter while seeking non-emergency care. In this unique position, they are poised to directly provide care and help coordinate patients' access to a variety of medical and healthcare services and programs. Consequently, it is vital that they are well-versed in the prompt identification, screening, diagnosis, treatment, and ongoing management of chronic illnesses such as Hepatitis-C. However, there are often barriers to treatment by

PCPs; these have been identified in several studies and journal articles (McGowan et al., 2013; Mitruka et al., 2014; Moore & Manch, 2013).

Knowledge-deficits about HCV prevalence, risk factors, and management strategies have been identified amongst healthcare providers (Mitchell, Colvin, & Palmer, 2010). In PCPs, a lack of HCV patient experience was cited as a factor; 73% of those surveyed saw less than five patients the earlier year, and 44% reported no experience with HCV treatment. Only half of the patients were referred to liver disease specialists (Grebely et al., 2009). Falade-Nwulia et al. (2016) studied 271 PCPs on preparedness to treat HCV patients. They reported that the PCPs who most appropriately treated this diagnosis were those in a practice that cared for higher proportions of this patient population.

Primary Care Providers Role in Hepatitis-C Patient Management

The relevant literature vastly showed that PCPs are the most influential factor for the early identification, screening, diagnosis, treatment, and ongoing management of patients with Hepatitis-C. In recent years, several expert reports have highlighted the benefit of directing efforts at the early identification, screening, diagnosis, treatment, and the subsequent ongoing management of patients with Hepatitis-C disease progression. In a 2017 report, the National Academy of Sciences (NAS; formerly the Institute of Medicine [IOM]), proposed augmented public health efforts aimed at achieving an 85% reduction in viremic cases and 65% reduction in annual deaths from chronic HCV infection by 2030 when compared to 2015. A cumulative 28,800 deaths reduction between 2015 and 2030 would be possible. Similar degrees of aggressive screening and treatment efforts would reduce HCV infection incidents by 90% by 2030 when compared

to 2015 (NAS, 2017; USDHHS, 2017). Regrettably, the evidence shows that PCPs have an HCV knowledge-deficit on several fronts including disease progression, risk factors, and who best to target as the highest priority for screening and testing according to guidelines (Jorgensen, Lewis, & Liu, 2012; NAS, 2017).

Primary Care Providers' Hepatitis-C Knowledge

The issue of PCP knowledge-deficit related to HCV infection has been well-documented within the U.S. and internationally by several studies. In their survey of a sample of American Academy of Family Physicians (AAFP) members, Clark, Yawn, Galliher, Temte, and Hickner (2005) found that the majority thought family physicians should screen (94%), diagnose (98%), and provide treatment and ongoing management (69%) for HCV patients. However, although they were aware of how to identify HCV patients most favored referring patients to Hepatologists for management. Similarly, in a more recent study by Thomson, Konerman, Choxi, and Lok (2016), although most PCPs surveyed accurately identified high-risk HCV patients, 19%, and 45% were unable to identify the birth-cohort group and hemodialysis patients respectively as higher risk populations. Seventy-one percent indicated they favored referring newly diagnosed patients to Hepatologists while 70% indicated a lack of current HCV treatment knowledge. Another instance of PCPs general HCV knowledge-deficit was recognized in a retrospective study that found PCPs did not screen 92% of patients with HCV risk factors for HCV (Almario, Vega, Trooskin, & Navarro, 2012).

Internationally, the issue of PCP knowledge-deficit related to HCV has similarly been explored by several studies (Cox et al., 2011; D'Souza, Glynn, Alstead, Osonayo, & Foster, 2004; Joukar, Mansour-Ghanaei, Soati, & Meskinkhoda, 2012; McGowan et al.,

2013). McGowan et al. (2013) in their global survey of providers that spanned 29 countries found that only 40% of respondents believed health care providers have adequate knowledge of HCV treatment guidelines. D'Souza, Glynn, Alstead, Osonayo, and Foster (2004) in their study of English providers found that PCPs could identify IV drug use as a risk factor for HCV transmission but were less successful at identifying other significant risk factors.

Therefore, learning what knowledge gaps exist amongst PCPs and how best to target educational strategies to address them, requires an understanding of the pre-existing HCV practice patterns of PCPs. Several studies have explored the issue of practice patterns and found several contributing factors. These factors include a lack of use of standardized screening tools to identify potential HCV patients, failed routine testing of high-risk populations, failed understanding of the testing sequence for HCV, and failed routine counseling of patients about the importance of changing high-risk behaviors such as IVDA or alcoholism (Almario et al., 2012; Clark, Yawn, Galliher, Temte, & Hickner, 2005; Fultz et al., 2003; Peksen et al., 2004). The appraisal of pre-existing practice patterns is particularly significant because most HCV patients are asymptomatic or present with non-specific symptoms until liver damage has manifested. Thus, the importance of the early identification, screening, diagnosis, treatment, ongoing management and referral to experts if necessary, of these individuals cannot be overemphasized.

Primary Care Providers' Hepatitis-C Practice Patterns

In addressing the issue of practice patterns as it pertains to the treatment and ongoing management of HCV patients, several studies examined the degree of

competency of PCPs, their ability to readily identify risk factors, their rationales for employing screening guidelines, and whether health promotion and disease prevention strategies were applied. The degree of PCP HCV management ability was examined by a study that found that 73% of those surveyed saw less than five patients the prior year, and 44% reported no experience with HCV treatment. Only half of the patients were referred to liver disease specialists (Grebely et al., 2009). This finding poses a grave problem on several fronts because the typical PCP with an average patient panel of 2,000 could potentially have 36 who are infected with HCV (Clark et al., 2005). Interestingly, although most of the PCPs in several studies were able to identify significant risk factors for HCV, a rather high percentage still erroneously considered casual household contact and blood transfusions after 1992 when stronger screening guidelines were instituted as a significant risk factor (Peksen et al., 2004; Shehab, Sonnad & Lok, 2001; Southern et al., 2011).

Shehab, Sonnad, and Lok (2001) in their study found that although more than 90% of PCPs appropriately identified the most common risk factors of HCV, only 59% indicated they ask all patients about HCV risk factors. Seventy percent tested all patients with HCV risk factors and 78% routinely tested all patients with elevated liver enzymes for Hepatitis-C. Also, 72% indicated they would refer patients with elevated liver enzymes to specialists; only 28% would refer patients with normal levels. Unfortunately, 25% of the PCPs indicated a lack of awareness of treatment guidelines for HCV patients. The researchers concluded that HCV patients were potentially underdiagnosed and under referred, which thus magnifies the need for the targeted educational and practice guidelines to augment PCP competency in this area.

Similarly, Cozzolongo, Cuppone, Petruzzi, Stroffolini, and Manghisi (2005) in their study of Italian PCPs at two different periods found that up to 27% still believed that blood transfusions after 1992 was an HCV risk factor. 38% of PCPs indicated that they would refer HCV-positive patients with abnormal liver enzymes to specialists. The researchers thus concluded that the overall HCV patient management practice patterns of PCPs could be enhanced using educational activities involving actively and interactively engaged PCPs. These studies illustrate the fact that although PCPs are knowledgeable about most aspects of HCV, they lack the experience in consistently managing patients that may include referral to specialists.

Arming PCPs with the knowledge to augment their competency in the subject matter, therefore, can best be accomplished by the design, implementation, and evaluation of an effective educational intervention. However, PCPs often cite time constraints as a significant factor in the inability to attend a formal, structured in-person educational offering such as a live conference. Alternative educational methods such as computerized modalities are therefore highly desirable as they bring the learning directly to the learner. Arora et al. (2011) found the use of the Extension for Community Healthcare Outcomes (ECHO) telemedicine modality to expose PCPs to liver disease specialists' knowledge as an effective means to improve competency.

Origins of Extension for Community Healthcare Outcomes (ECHO)

The genesis for the idea of the Extension for Community Healthcare Outcomes (ECHO) project was Dr. Sanjeev Arora, who is a Liver Disease Specialist at the University of New Mexico Health Sciences Center in Albuquerque (University of New Mexico, 2018). Dr. Arora has garnered a reputation as a visionary in the use of telehealth

medium for the dissemination of expert knowledge to providers across geographical distances. Numerous studies have highlighted the merits of using the ECHO project concept, and it has thus been adopted across the U.S. and the globe. There are more than 23 countries worldwide using the concept to address over 70 multifaceted health conditions and complications. The ECHO concept has even crossed over to other professional fields including its use by the University of Wyoming in sharing assistive technologies expertise with special education teachers in public schools (University of New Mexico, 2018). Although it was initially used for the management of liver patients, the ECHO concept has since been used across other healthcare specialties.

Evidence of ECHO Usage across Healthcare and Beyond

Masi et al. (2012) used the ECHO concept to augment hypertension (HTN) management knowledge and self-evaluated competence of primary care providers (PCPs) employed across 6 urban Federally Qualified Health Centers (FQHCs). The University of Chicago Pritzker School of Medicine, Chicago, IL acted as the expert site providing the telehealth HTN specialist support. There were twelve 1-hour sessions during which PCPs received a brief lecture, made case presentations of their own and engaged in interactive dialogues. Twelve PCPs (9 intervention and 3 controls) who were surveyed at pre- and post-participation had varying scores. On the 26-item HTN knowledge questionnaire, the intervention group had higher (17.44 from 13.11) mean number of correct answers from the baseline. The intervention group similarly scored higher on the 7-item HTN management self-assessed competency scale from baseline; 4.68 to 5.41. Thus, the researchers concluded that the use of the ECHO concept had good potential for augmenting the HTN care provision skills of the urban FQHC providers.

Katzman et al. (2014) used the ECHO concept to help improve pain management skills of PCPs in primary care. During an almost 3-year period, 136 Project ECHO Pain clinic sessions took place involving 763 PCPs across 191 diverse locations with 3835 total participation times. Three measures were used to evaluate the success of the series: (1) weekly continuing medical education surveys; (2) annual clinic data aggregation; and (3) practice change assessment in clinicians who took part for at least a year. At least 66% of participants self-identified as being non-physician health professionals such as Nurse Practitioners. The overall results demonstrated significant improvement in self-reported knowledge, skills, and practice by participants. Additionally, a focus group analysis of 9 participants specifically detailed their practice improvements. Thus, the benefits of using it in the VHA was supported.

Implementation of SCAN-ECHO within the Veterans Health Administration (VHA)

The Veterans Health Administration's (VHA) SCAN-ECHO concept borrows from the outreach program developed by the University of New Mexico Project ECHO discussed earlier. Much like its parent concept, the VHA SCAN-ECHO allows specialty care teams in such areas as diabetes, pain management, cardiology, dermatology, and Hepatitis-C to utilize video conferencing technology to connect with local PCPs. The use of the SCAN-ECHO videoconferencing program between PCPs and specialists educates providers in the delivery of specialty care from a distance, potentially improving healthcare delivery.

Salgia, McCurdy, and Moseley (2014) surveyed 51 PCPs who took part in a SCAN-ECHO series at a VHA facility on their reasons for taking part and the impact on their practice. Twenty-four responded indicating that their participation was fueled by a

strong desire to be versed in HCV knowledge and apply it to the care of potential patients, and the need to save their patients time and energy expended on referrals to outside experts.

Summary

This review of the literature used original research published in peer-reviewed journals and by suitable national and international professional and governmental agencies such as the CDC and the WHO. The issue of the need for adequate PCP management of HCV patients was the emerging theme that was well-detailed throughout. The effectiveness of the use of the ECHO concept to expose PCPs to subject-matter experts in such areas as pain management, HTN management, and liver disease management was explicit. Several studies have illustrated the fact that veteran patients tend to have higher HCV rates than the general population (Bakr et al., 2018; Dominitz et al., 2005). The challenge for PCPs with the VHA system, therefore, is to direct efforts at programs and services targeting this group of patients. Seeking the knowledge of subject-matter experts as allowed using SCAN-ECHO to provide training such as occurred in the 2016 pilot that is the impetus for this DNP project adds to this wealth of evidentiary resources as has been shown through this literature review.

METHODS

According to Polit and Beck (2017), “the methods section describes the methods used to answer the research questions. This section lays out methodologic decisions made in the design and planning phase (Phase 2) and may offer rationales for those decisions” (p. 61). This DNP quality improvement project, therefore, was undertaken to evaluate the impact of an earlier program conducted at a large urban Veterans Administration Medical Center (VAMC) Healthcare System in Southern California. The continuing education program that started with a pilot in summer 2016 involved the use of a hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational series to augment the HCV patient management skills of PCPs in the Homeless Patient-Aligned Care Team (HPACT).

The pilot involved 6 HPACT PCPs who took part in 2-3 educational sessions on HCV treatment that included handouts on patient selection criteria. Subsequently, the educational series was rolled-out to include all 21 PCPs assigned to the HPACT. Thus, this DNP project evaluation involved ascertaining improved provider Hepatitis-C knowledge, confidence, and behavioral attitudes, along with figuring out the extent to which the participation in the hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational series improved their skills in the management of Hepatitis-C patients.

Setting

This DNP quality improvement project was undertaken at a large urban VAMC Healthcare System in Southern California. There are 21 PCPs including physicians, NPs, mental health providers, and clinical pharmacists assigned to the HPACT for this facility who participated in the hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational series. The HPACT providers

refer HCV patients to and consult with the Liver Clinic for specialized management as the need arises.

Sample

Inclusion criteria for the project were all PCPs in the HPACT including nurse practitioners, preceptees, and medical interns and residents who took part in the hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational series since its 2016 pilot inception. The total number was 21 providers. The inclusion of everyone aimed to assess for any possible variances between provider groups who received the training in terms of the perception of improved confidence in knowledge, management skills, and behavioral attitudes about Hepatitis-C.

Procedures

First, during the first week of January 2019, the PCPs were sent an e-mail to all known e-mail addresses for them (See Appendix A) inviting their participation. The fact that the e-mail was read was acknowledged with the automatic “read receipt” generated by the organization’s Outlook E-mail system as enabled by the DNP student researcher at the time of sending the e-mail. The PCPs then clicked on a web link within the e-mail that took them to the online SurveyMonkey website to complete the anonymous survey. The consent for participation was shown by the participant’s completion of the online survey. The e-mail invitation was sent three separate times within six weeks, but not all participants responded by the end of this timeframe. Although, there was no automatic thank-you e-mail sent to participants immediately after their completed survey was received during the initial period in January, the subsequent reminder e-mails did contain a thank-you to all those who completed the survey at that time.

Second, during mid-February 2019 the PCPs were then sent another invitation to participate via an e-mail link sent directly from the SurveyMonkey website (Appendix B). This invitation process included sending an automatic thank-you e-mail to participants immediately after their completed survey was received. A reminder was sent seven days after the initial invitation then again at 14 days afterward to individuals with no response or partial response. Participants were offered no gifts or inducements for survey completion.

There was an available validated tool that the DNP student researcher reviewed to ascertain its appropriateness for adaptation for use. The tool known as the NUTCOMP Tool was developed by Australian researchers (Ball & Leveritt, 2015) to measure the self-perceived competence of primary health interprofessionals in providing nutrition care to patients with chronic disease. Therefore, the focus of the tool is like the evaluation of the self-perceived improved competence of PCPs in HCV patient care management, which is the emphasis of this DNP project. Thus, an e-mail was sent to the developer(s) requesting a complete copy and permission to adapt and use accordingly.

The tool was adapted (See Appendix D) for this project after the related permission request was granted via e-mail (See Appendix C) by the developer(s). The results of the literature review guided the adaptation of the tool as the included questions took into consideration the themes that emerged such as PCP use of USPSTF guidelines to evaluate the appropriateness of an individual's HCV screening against risk factors, PCP ability to evaluate HCV infected patients' candidacy for treatment, et cetera. The adapted survey included open-ended and closed-ended questions (not used in the original tool) to allow for analysis of variation in the response patterns of participants. The

purpose was to enable a functional analysis of the data. The NUTCOMP Tool was adapted to be the HEP-C PATIENT MANAGEMENT COMPETENCY Tool (See Appendix D).

Ethical Issues

Explanation of the DNP quality improvement project was fully disclosed to all participants as evidenced by the recruitment e-mail sent to them and participant information sheet as displayed within the online survey on the SurveyMonkey website (See Appendix B). PCP participation was voluntary. Although demographic data was gathered about the PCPs, the DNP student researcher ensured confidentiality by reporting de-identified aggregated data only. During data gathering, extraction, and evaluation, individual PCPs were not identified to safeguard data confidentiality. The DNP student researcher who is also an employee of the organization administered the survey then completed the data gathering and extraction and then analyzed with the assistance of the DNP Project Team Leader who is the faculty adviser.

A required preliminary Institutional Review Board (IRB) application known as Form-00 was initially submitted to the healthcare system. Upon IRB review, it was determined that the evaluation of PCPs perceived improved Hepatitis-C management skills after the hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational series was a quality improvement (QI) project and not a human subject research study (See Appendix E). The organizational IRB determination was then submitted to the California State University at Los Angeles (CSULA) IRB. The CSULA IRB concurred with the healthcare system that full IRB approval was unnecessary (See Appendix E).

Planning the Quality Improvement Program

The Associate Chief of Division of Infectious Diseases at the large urban VAMC, which was the setting sought the implementation of the QI project. The purpose was the need for evaluation of the perceptions of improved HCV patient care management skills competency by the PCPs because of having participated in the hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational series. The DNP student researcher collaborated with the Chief to outline the details before proceeding to conduct the QI project. The Chief was also quite helpful in providing feedback on the survey instrument that was adapted for use in this QI project.

Methods of Evaluation

Transformations in the participants' knowledge, skills, or attitudes (KSA) as can be confirmed by the administration of a survey was the aim. There was no additional training needed as the DNP student researcher solely administered the survey and performed the data collection. The PCP demographic data collected included: age, race, gender, number of years of practice and type of professional status. Other data collected included how many sessions of the hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational series attended and perceptions of its impact on improved Hepatitis-C management skills and practice.

Primary outcome measures were the PCPs perceptions of improved self-competency after the hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational series. Secondary outcome measures included the subjective perceptions of the PCPs of the adequacy of how the hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational and management series improved their management of HCV types of patients. Therefore, the overall project questions intended to be answered was accomplished by the following means:

1. Did participation in the hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational and management series in 2016 result in perceived improved confidence in knowledge about Hepatitis-C and chronic disease?
 - a. Administration of an online survey (See Appendix D).
2. Did participation in the hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational and management series in 2016 result in perceived improved confidence in Hepatitis-C management skills?
 - a. Administration of an online survey (See Appendix D).
3. What are the attitudes of PCPs who participated in the hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational and management series in 2016 towards HCV patient care?
 - a. Administration of an online survey (See Appendix D).
4. Will PCPs report that participation in the hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational and management series in 2016 resulted in improvement of their management of HCV types of patients?
 - a. Administration of an online survey (See Appendix D).

A theory-of-change logic model was utilized to give a pictorial depiction of how the project worked. According to the Center for Community Health and Development at the University of Kansas (2018),

“A logic model presents a picture of how your effort or initiative is supposed to work. It explains why your strategy is a good solution to the problem at hand. Effective logic models make an explicit, often visual, statement of the activities that will bring about change and the results you expect to see for the community and its people. A logic

model keeps participants in the effort moving in the same direction by providing a common language and point of reference.” (University of Kansas, 2018).

Inputs (What is invested) Mobilized Resources	Outputs (What to be done and who does it) Activities and Interventions		Outcomes – Impact (The incremental events/changes that occur as a result of the outputs)		
	Activities	Participation	Short	Medium	Long
	Time (DNP student researcher, DNP faculty adviser, & PCPs) Computers (already available within the organization)	Technology Use Recruitment e-mail to PCPs Online survey completion Data collection Data analysis	DNP student researcher, PCPs, DNP faculty adviser DNP student researcher PCPs DNP student researcher DNP student researcher, DNP faculty adviser	100% of PCPs are aware of the current HCV QI project via sent e-mail notification by the end of Mar'19 50% of PCPs complete survey by the end of Jan'19 - Send 1 st e-mail reminder 1-wk after initial notification 75% of PCPs complete survey by the end of Feb'19 - Send 2 nd e-mail reminder 3 rd wk of Feb'19; if not ALL have responded 100% PCPs complete survey w/ data analysis done by the end of Mar'19 - Send final e-mail reminder the 1 st wk of Mar'19	25% of PCPs complete online survey promptly 50% of PCPs complete online survey promptly 75% of PCPs complete online survey promptly 100% of PCPs complete online survey promptly Data analysis is done & completed by the end of 2 nd wk of Mar'19 80% of PCPs self-reporting improved HCV patient management skills
ASSUMPTIONS (root cause analyses, prior learning/experience) PCPs want to learn of the impact of the 2016 pilot study on improved practice; PCPs will be receptive to participation in the current project; surveys will be completed promptly/adequately.			EXTERNAL FACTORS (barriers/facilitators) Day-to-day organizational computer server issues and HPACT patient care management demands on PCPs may affect the set timeline(s).		

Figure 2. Supporting framework applied to data-gathering and analysis process.

RESULTS

The purpose of this project was to evaluate the impact of the hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational and management series on perceptions by participating PCPs at a local VHA healthcare system of increased competency in the identification, screening, diagnosis, treatment and ongoing management of patients with Hepatitis-C. The administration of a survey helped to accomplish this. The objective was to ascertain the following: (1) whether PCPs indicated they had felt more confident in their knowledge of Hepatitis-C and chronic care, (2) whether they felt more confident in their ability to manage HCV patients, (3) whether the knowledge change improved their overall attitudes about skills and practice management of HCV patients, and (4) whether they reported that participation in the hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational and management series in 2016 resulted in overall improvement of their management of HCV types of patients.

The sample consisted of all providers (N=21) who were identified as having participated in the hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational series since its 2016 inception. All were sent the recruitment e-mail for this QI project survey. Ten completed the survey for a response rate of 48%, and thus this is the sample population for the project data analysis. Time spent to complete the survey took less than 6 minutes.

The survey variables were as follows: (1) confidence in knowledge about Hepatitis-C and chronic disease; (2) confidence in Hepatitis-C management skills; (3) attitudes towards HCV patient care; (4) how participation in the previous SCAN-ECHO educational series has improved their management of HCV types of patients; and (5) demographics.

Descriptive Statistics

The demographic analysis of the project participants included gender, age, racial/ethnic background, professional background type, and the number of years of practice. Participants were 60% female. They ranged in age from 35-44 years (60%) to 65 years of age (20%) with 10% declining to answer the question (table 1). The professional designation was 50% physicians and 50% nurse practitioners. The most extended years in practice was 40 years, and the shortest was one year.

Survey Responses

A Likert-like scale was used to measure eleven items which reflected three content areas: (1) participants confidence in knowledge about Hepatitis-C and chronic disease; (2) confidence in Hepatitis-C management skills; and (3) attitudes towards HCV patient care. A presentation of the analysis of the response variances is as follows.

Descriptive statistics were calculated for each item. Variables then were analyzed using a contingency table to determine associations and interrelationship between variables and professional designation. According to Polit and Beck (2017), “a crosstabs table (or contingency table) is a two-dimensional frequency distribution in which the frequencies of two variables are cross-tabulated.” (p. 364). In this survey, the only demographic variable demonstrating a statistically relevant relationship with content area items was a professional designation.

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics Summary

Variable	Total	Percentage
Gender		
Male	4	40%
Female	6	60%
TOTALS	10	100%
Ethnicity/Race		
White/Caucasian	4	40%
Hispanic/Non-black	2	20%
Asian/Asian American	1	10%
Another Race	1	10%
Decline to Answer	2	20%
TOTALS	10	100%
Age		
35-44	6	60%
45-64	1	10%
65 and older	2	20%
Prefer not to answer	1	10%
TOTALS	10	100%
Profession		
MD	5	50%
NP	5	50%
TOTALS	10	100%
Number of Sessions Attended		
1 session	2	20%
≥ 3 sessions	8	80%
TOTALS	10	100%

Confidence in Knowledge about Hepatitis-C and Chronic Disease

Confidence in knowledge about Hepatitis-C and chronic disease was assessed with five items (Appendix D, section 1). Overall, physicians were most confident in their knowledge of how different population groups were at risk for the development of Hepatitis-C with 80% rating themselves as extremely confident or somewhat confident (20%). While the nurse practitioners rated themselves as very confident (80%) or extremely confident (20%).

The nurse practitioners mostly rated themselves as somewhat confident (60%) when indicating their knowledge of the most recently published peer-reviewed evidence regarding the care of the patient with Hepatitis-C and chronic Hepatitis-C management. Conversely, the physicians mostly rated themselves as extremely confident (60%).

There were similarities and differences between nurse practitioners and physicians. Both nurse practitioners (80% very confident) and physicians (80% extremely confident) reported significant confidence in their knowledge of which groups were at higher risk for developing Hepatitis-C (Figure 3). Nurse practitioners reported higher levels of confidence about knowledge of risk factors than physicians. Both groups indicated varied confidence in their knowledge about treatment guidelines. Knowledge of peer-reviewed evidence demonstrated discrepant responses from extremely confident (60%), somewhat confident (20%) to not-so-confident (20%) among physicians and extremely confident (20%), very confident (20%) to somewhat confident (60%) among nurse practitioners. Physicians indicated higher levels of confidence about their knowledge of pharmacology and pharmacotherapeutics of medications used for Hepatitis-C treatment (Figure 3).

Confidence in Knowledge about Hepatitis-C and Chronic Disease

Figure 3. Confidence in knowledge about Hepatitis-C and chronic disease.

Confidence in Hepatitis-C Management Skills

Confidence in Hepatitis C management skills was assessed with 3 items (Appendix D, section 2). Overall, primary care providers were extremely confident in their ability to interpret lab data about viral Hepatitis-C antibody screen; viral Hepatitis-C RNA by PCR; Hepatitis-C virus genotype with physicians being higher (60% vs. 40%) than nurse practitioners. Conversely, only 40% of the nurse practitioners rated themselves as extremely confident in their ability to use the USPSTF guidelines to evaluate the appropriateness of an individual's HCV screening against risk factors.

There were similarities and differences between nurse practitioners and physicians. Nurses and physicians both reported feeling somewhat confident in their ability to evaluate HCV infected patients' candidacy for treatment, including the evaluation of patient factors (liver disease staging, psychosocial determinants) and viral factors (HCV genotype, treatment-experience) in assessing the HCV treatment regimen (Figure 4). Although, there was an equal percentage of both groups indicating less confidence in their ability to evaluate HCV infected patients' candidacy for treatment, physicians generally reported higher levels of confidence about their ability (Figure 4). The ability to interpret lab data about viral Hepatitis-C antibody screen demonstrated discrepant responses from extremely confident (40%) to somewhat confident (20%) among nurse practitioners to extremely confident (60%) to not-so-confident (40%) among physicians. The ability to use USPSTF guidelines to evaluate the appropriateness of an individual's HCV screening against risk factors also demonstrated discrepant responses from extremely confident (60%), somewhat confident (20%) to not-so-confident (20%) among physicians to extremely confident (40%) to very confident (60%) among nurse practitioners (Figure 4).

Confidence in Hepatitis-C Management Skills

Figure 4. Confidence in Hepatitis-C management skills.

Attitudes Towards HCV Patient Care

Attitudes towards HCV patient care were assessed with 3 items (Appendix D, section 3). Overall, primary care providers strongly agreed that it is essential that all individuals born between 1945-1965 be screened for HCV regardless of age, race, and risk factors. Physicians and nurse practitioners both strongly agreed that encouraging patients/clients to avoid HCV risky behaviors is an effective use of their professional time although the nurse practitioners (80% vs. 60%) indicated that they strongly agree (Figure 5).

There were again similarities and differences between nurse practitioners and physicians. Nurse practitioners and physicians both reported that it is essential that they refer patients/clients to other health care professionals if they are unable to meet their HCV-related care management need although nurse practitioners more overwhelmingly (100% vs. 80%) strongly agreed. The importance of encouraging patients/clients to avoid HCV risky behaviors as effective use of their professional time demonstrated discrepant responses from strongly agree (60%), to agree (20%), to non-response (20%) among physicians. Nurse practitioners consistently indicated higher levels of positiveness of attitudes about HCV patient care (figure 5).

Attitudes Towards HCV Patient Care

Figure 5. Attitudes towards HCV patient care.

Motivation for Participation

The number of sessions attended by participants varied from 1 (20%) to ≥ 3 (80%) with the primary motivation for attendance varying from curiosity (20%), increase my knowledge (30%), and gain new knowledge (50%). A contingency table showing the frequency distribution of the responses is presented (Table 2). Nurse Practitioners (80%) indicated that they attended for the opportunity to gain new knowledge (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Motivation for participation.

Table 2

*Profession * Motivation for Participation Crosstabulation*

Count		Curiosity	Increase knowledge & improve experience	Gain new knowledge	Total
profession	MD	2	2	1	5
	NP	0	1	4	5
Total		2	3	5	10

Phi = .127

Narrative Responses

The participants responded to the question “How has your participation in the Hepatitis-C hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational and management series in 2016 improved your management of HCV types of patients?” All participants responded (table 3). Most participants indicated improved knowledge and confidence in caring for this patient population. However, one noted that he was already quite expert. Others (participant 2 and 3) noted a better understanding and appreciation of the role of interprofessional collaboration in caring for these patients. Five participants commented on their increased ability to diagnosis and treat patients with HCV.

Table 3

Narrative Responses of Participation Impact

“ Improved knowledge, competence , and confidence .” (Participant 1)
“ Increased confidence in diagnosing and initiating tx as well as collaborating on an interprofessional level.” (Participant 2)
“ Improved my appreciation of the importance of multi-disciplinary teams.” (Participant 3)
“ Identification of patients eligible for treatment.” (Participant 4)
“SCAN-ECHO helped me solidify my understanding and interpretation of lab results, imaging and overall management of HCV.” (Participant 5)
“YES.” (Participant 6)
“I have gained additional clinical and systems-based knowledge to optimally treat patients for HCV in the primary care setting. I systematically encourage patients to obtain evaluation for and treatment of HCV. The SCAN ECHO team has been fantastic in encouraging PCP participation and building capacity to treat patients in their medical home setting.” (Participant 7)
“I was already quite expert.” (Participant 8)
“I received extensive exposure to patients with Hepatitis C. I am comfortable in working up a patient who is requesting Hep C treatment.” (Participant 9)
“Better understanding of HCV risk factors, lab interpretation and treatment options.” (Participant 10)

DISCUSSION

There have been overwhelming recommendations by various official bodies about the ongoing need for primary care provider proficiency in the identification, screening, treatment, and management of patients at risk for HCV to mitigate disease development and the sometimes-deadly evolution of this highly treatable infection (Aspinall et al., 2015). This scholarly DNP project aimed to evaluate improved Hepatitis-C patient management skills as perceived by primary care providers after participating in a hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational and management series. The goal was to determine the extent to which participants believed that they increased their knowledge and skills in the management of this patient population.

The hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational series was delivered in a synchronous, webinar format with the ability to communicate with presenters and other participants in real-time. Quantitative and narrative responses support that SCAN-ECHO participants perceived that their knowledge and skills for Hepatitis-C management were enhanced by exposure to experts via this educational method. Webinar formats have been recognized as an effective method of delivering content in previous health education research (McKinney, 2017). The most often employed evaluation method for the impact of webinars is a survey measuring participants' self-perceived increased competence and knowledge (McKinney, 2017). However, the impact of this learning methodology on measurable changes in provider practice and patient outcomes is limited (McKinney, 2017). Like findings in the literature, the age of the participant did not appear to impact the acceptability of this learning method. Instead, the literature noted that education

delivered at point-of-contact which allows for less time away from the clinical area was essential (Cook et al., 2018).

Respondents were equally divided among nurse practitioners and physicians. Although 21 PCPs received the SCAN-ECHO training, only 10 participated in this program impact evaluation QI project. The response rate for the evaluation survey administered via the SurveyMonkey website was 48%, which is aligned with the less than 50% expected rate that has been identified by experts for surveys delivered online (Polit & Beck 2017). Nevertheless, there could have been additional means utilized to augment the response rate as has been noted in the literature. Brtnikova et al. (2018) over six years examined methods to augment survey response rates without the use of enticements, the usefulness of repeated survey reminders, and any differences in response rates based on survey mode and primary care specialty of their study participants. They found that the highest response rates were achieved in the email group when the nine contact efforts by email were followed by up to 3 attempts by mail, with the last mail effort including additional features such as hand-addressing the envelopes. Dillman, Smyth, and Christian (2009) in their study supported this in suggesting that the last effort have a different appearance than previous efforts, because “stimuli that are different from previous ones are generally more powerful than the repetition of a previously used technique.” Other studies have used this approach with similar outcomes.

The question that measured motivation demonstrated significantly different responses between physicians and nurse practitioners. The younger, less experienced nurse practitioners mostly identified the need to gain new knowledge as their motivation, while physicians indicated that they participated either to increase their knowledge or

“just for curiosity.” Research on primary care providers including nurse practitioners demonstrated a perceived lack of knowledge in the assessment and management of this patient population (Naghdi et al., 2017). However, because some of the physician participants involved in this QI project are assigned to the Liver Clinic; they would be expected to have significantly more experience than other participants.

When physicians were compared to nurse practitioners, there was generally minimal variation in their responses across all study variables. The physician group who were older had more experience in their roles. Narrative responses indicated that most participants felt that their participation in the Hepatitis-C hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational and management series improved their identification and management of HCV patients. Many indicated an improved understanding of the vital role of interprofessional management. However, an accurate measure of the efficacy of this training cannot be achieved without a planned evaluation of its impact on patient referral rates and outcome data subsequently.

The number of sessions participated in did not appear to change perceived competence amongst study participants. In other words, those who only participated in one session were just as likely as those who participated in three or more sessions to report that they felt more competent in their identification and management of HCV patients. This is like the findings by Traphagan, Kucsera, and Kishi (2010) who found in their study of the impact of class lecture webcasts on students' attendance and learning that webcasts could positively impact students' learning experiences and performance, even in the presence of limited class attendance.

Although this element of whether the number of sessions attended affected their perception of improved competency was not collected in the descriptive or demographic data, it is postulated that this may in part be related to differences in the participants' previous experience with this population. Also, the motivation for participation did not appear to change knowledge variables. The PCPs, nevertheless, collectively described improved knowledge, skill, and self-confidence in managing HCV types of patients as a result of having participated.

Limitations

The key limitation of the project was the sample size, which generally resulted in a homogenous response pattern amongst and between provider profession groups. Because all participants received the initial e-mail invitation to complete the online survey via the healthcare system's Outlook e-mail, there was no mechanism to send an automatic thank-you e-mail immediately after their completed survey was received. Sending the invitation directly via the SurveyMonkey e-mail link from the onset, as was eventually done, would have perhaps resulted in a higher response rate. The justification to send the invitation as was initially done via the healthcare system's internal e-mail system was that participants would be more likely to complete the survey having realized that it came directly from a colleague.

Recommendations

A replication of this QI project with new participants incorporating the lessons learned from this one would be beneficial. For future surveys, data should also be collected about prior experience and training in the management of Hepatitis-C patients. A pretest with identical posttest would supply an accurate measure of knowledge

acquisition versus self-perception of changes in knowledge, skills, and attitudes. Finally, a patient outcome measure tracking the referrals and appropriateness of treatment from participants with time would be invaluable in determining the efficacy of the education.

Implications for Practice

According to the CDC (2019), there was a total of 2,967 cases of acute Hepatitis-C reported to the CDC from 42 states in 2016. Alarming, almost fifty percent of the 3.5 million people currently living with Hepatitis-C in the U.S. are unaware of their infection. The healthcare burden of undiagnosed and untreated Hepatitis-C can be astronomical with the impact highest in underserved communities. According to data from 2012, Medicaid covered over 12% of liver transplant patients with HCV with the typical cost of a liver transplant due to HCV estimated at \$188,000 (Younossi et al., 2001). Another study specified that Medicaid pays an estimated \$147 million annually for liver transplantation in addition to the substantial costs of post-transplant immunosuppressive therapy and ongoing management of potential significant complications (Johnson, Blumen, & Ferro, 2015). There is, therefore, a great need for healthcare providers including PCPs to more readily and effectively identify, screen, treat, and manage patients at risk for HCV to mitigate disease development and the too often deadly evolution of this highly treatable infection (Aspinall et al., 2015; Samuel et al., 2018).

The benefit of QI projects such as this one undertaken by this by this DNP final project is invaluable. They illuminate the fact that exposure to content-experts such as Hepatologists via structured educational mediums such as hybrid SCAN-ECHO webinars even for one session can positively augment PCP self-perceived improved competency in the identification, screening, treatment, and management of patients at risk for HCV.

However, this is only achievable through a concerted effort pooling together the resources of an interdisciplinary team. Involving the frontline nursing staff with whom patients first interact upon presentation for clinic appointments, the PCP who provides the medical intervention, the Pharmacist who addresses medication prescription issues, the Dietician or Nutritionist who addresses nutritional issues, and the Social Worker who may have to connect the patient to much-needed community resources is invaluable. Doing so does not require a radical restructuring of usual standard operating procedures (SOPs) nor the expenditure of additional financial and human capital. Instead, it merely involves considering the breadth of the interplay of knowledge, skills, and attitudes impacting effective identification, screening, treatment, and management of patients at risk for HCV to mitigate disease development and ease the healthcare burden of this sometimes fatal but very treatable infection (Aspinall et al., 2015; Samuel et al., 2018).

Conclusion

With the ubiquitous presence of technological innovations to provide mass education across geographical distances, it is advantageous to employ this medium to spread specialty knowledge to healthcare providers such as PCPs. The results of this QI project indicated that PCPs do perceive, and report enhanced knowledge, skills, and attitudes when exposed to specialty experts via a medium such as a hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational and management series. Resultantly, the cumulative effect of more readily identifying, screening, treating, and managing patients at risk for HCV, particularly those in the birth cohort-based group significantly contributes to the effective use of healthcare resources to avert disease development and the sometimes-terminal progression of this decidedly curable infection.

REFERENCES

- Almario, C. V., Vega, M., Trooskin, S. B., & Navarro, V. J. (2012). Examining hepatitis C virus testing practices in primary care clinics. *Journal of Viral Hepatitis*, *19*(2), e163-e169. Retrieved from www.medscape.com
- Averhoff, F. M., Glass, N., & Holtzman, D. (2012). Global burden of hepatitis C: Considerations for healthcare providers in the United States. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*, *55*(S1), S10–S15. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/cis361>
- Arora, S., Thornton, K., Murata, J., Deming, P., Kalishman, S., Dion, D., . . . Qualls, C. (2011). Outcome of treatments for hepatitis C virus infection by primary care providers. *The New England Journal of Medicine*, *364*, 2199-207. doi:10.1056/NEJMoa1009370
- Aspinall, E. J., Doyle, J. S., Corson, S., Hellard, M. E., Hunuyent, D., Goldberg, D., . . . Hutchinson, S. (2015). Targeted hepatitis C antibody testing interventions: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *European Journal of Epidemiology*, *30*, 115-129. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10654-014-9958-4>
- Bakr, O., Gelberg, L., Cowan, B., Seragaki, S., Youn, S., Kawamoto, J., . . . Bhattacharya, D. (2018). Treating Hepatitis C in the Homeless Patient-Aligned Care Team (HPACT) at the Greater Los Angeles VA – A pilot study. *Gastroenterology*, *154*(6), S-1105-S-1106. doi: 10.1016/S0016-5085(18)33675-8
- Ball, L. E., & Leveritt, M.D. (2015). Development of a validated questionnaire to measure the self-perceived competence of primary health professionals in providing nutrition care to patients with chronic disease. *Family Practice*, *00*(00), 1-5. doi:10.1093/fampra/cmz073

- Brtnikova, M., Crane, L.A., Allison, M.A., Hurley, L.P., Beaty, B.L., & Kempe, A. (2018). A method for achieving high response rates in national surveys of U.S. primary care physicians. *PLoS ONE*, *13*(8), e0202755. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0202755>
- Center for Community Health and Development at the University of Kansas. (2018). The Community Tool Box: Developing a logic model or theory of change. Retrieved from <https://ctb.ku.edu/en/table-of-contents/overview/models-for-community-health-and-development/logic-model-development/main>.
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC, 2016a). Viral hepatitis. Retrieved from <https://www.cdc.gov/hepatitis/hcv/cfaq.htm>
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC, 2016b). Hepatitis C kills more Americans than any other infectious disease. Retrieved from <https://www.cdc.gov/media/releases/2016/p0504-hepc-mortality.html>
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC, 2016c). Hepatitis C kills more Americans than any other infectious disease. Retrieved from <https://www.cdc.gov/nchhstp/newsroom/2016/hcv-press-release.html>
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC, 2013). Completeness of reporting of chronic hepatitis B and C virus infections — Michigan, 1995–2008. Retrieved from <https://www.cdc.gov/mmwr/preview/mmwrhtml/mm6206a2.htm>
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC, 2018). Logic Models. Retrieved from https://www.cdc.gov/eval/tools/evaluability_assessments/index.html

- Chak, E., Talal, A.H., Sherman, K.E., Schiff, E.R., & Saab, S. (2011). Hepatitis C virus infection in USA: An estimate of true prevalence. *Liver International*, *31*(8), 1090-1101. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1478-3231.2011.02494.x>
- Clark, E. C., Yawn, B. P., Galliher, J. M., Temte, J. L., & Hincker, J. (2005). Hepatitis C identification and management by family physicians. *Family Medicine*, *37*(9), 644-649.
- Cozzolongo, R., Cuppone, R., Petruzzi, J., Stroffolini, T., & Manghisi, O.G. (2005). Approach of primary care physicians to hepatitis C: An educational survey from a Southern Italian area. *Journal of Infection*, *51*(5), 396-400. doi: 10.1016/j.jinf.2004.12.004
- Cook, D.A., Blachman, M.J., Price, D.W., West, C.P., Baasch Thomas, B.L., Berger, R.A., . . . Wittich, C.M. (2018). Educational technologies for physician continuous professional development: A national survey. *Academic Medicine*, *93*(1), 104-112.
- Cox, J., Graves, L., Marks, E., Tremblay, C., Stephenson, R., Lambert-Lanning, A., & Steben, M. (2011). Knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors associated with the provision of hepatitis C care by Canadian family physicians. *Journal of Viral Hepatology*, *18*(7), e332-40. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2893.2010.01426.x.
- Coyle, C., Kwakwa, H., & Viner, K. (2016). Integrating routine HCV testing in primary care: Lessons learned from five federally qualified health centers in Philadelphia, Pennsylvania, 2012-2014. *Public Health Reports*, *2*(131), 65-73.
- Dillman, D.A., Smyth, J., & Christian, L.M. (2009). Internet, mail and mixed-mode surveys: The tailored design method. (3rd ed.). New York, NY: John Wiley Co.

- Dominitz, J. A., Boyko, E. J., Koepsell, T. D., Heagerty, P. J., Maynard, C., Sporleder, J. L., & VA Cooperative Study Group 488. (2005). Elevated prevalence of Hepatitis C infection in users of United States Veterans medical centers. *Hepatology, 41*(1), 88-96.
- D'Souza, R. F., Glynn, M. J., Alstead, E., Osonayo, C., & Foster, G. R. (2004). Knowledge of chronic hepatitis C among East London primary care physicians following the department of health educational campaign. *Quality Journal of Medicine, 97*, 331-336.
- Dultz, E., Graubard, B., Martin, P., Welker, M.W., Vermehren, J., Zeuzem, S., . . . Welzel, T.M. (2011). Liver transplantation for chronic hepatitis C virus infection in the United States 2002– 2014: An analysis of the UNOS/OPTN registry. *PLoS ONE, 12*(10), e0186898. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0186898>.
- Falade-Nwulia, O., McAdam-Mahmoud, A., Irvin, R., Niculescu, A., Page, K.R., Mix, M., ... Mehta, S.H. (2016). Primary care providers knowledge, attitude and practices related to hepatitis C screening and treatment in the oral direct antiviral agents era. *Journal of Community Medical Health Education, 6*(5), 1-11. doi:10.4172/2161-0711.1000481

- Fathauer, L., & Meek, J. (2012). Initial implementation and evaluation of a Hepatitis C treatment clinical decision support system (CDSS): A nurse practitioner-driven quality improvement initiative. *Applied Clinical Informatics, 3*(3), 337–348. doi: 10.4338/ACI-2012-04-RA-0012
- Fluhr, J. D., Oman, R. F., Allen, J. R., Lanphier, M. G., & McLeroy, K. R. (2004). A collaborative approach to program evaluation of community-based teen pregnancy prevention projects. *Health Promotion Practice, 5*(2), 127–137.
- Fultz, S. L., Justice, A. C., Butt, A. A., Rabeneck, L., Weissman, S., & Rodriguez-Barradas, M. (2003). Testing, referral, and treatment patterns for hepatitis C virus coinfection in a cohort of veterans with human immunodeficiency virus infection. *Clinical Infection Disease, 36*(8), 1039-1046. doi:10.1086/374049
- Government of South Australia. (2017). Nursing model of care for viral hepatitis management in South Australia. Retrieved from <http://www.sahealth.sa.gov.au/wps/wcm/connect/f5dc9e63-ad02-4d51-801c-164efc46143d/NursingMOCViralHepatitisManagementSA-CDCB-04122017.pdf?MOD=AJPERES&CACHEID=ROOTWORKSPACE-f5dc9e63-ad02-4d51-801c-164efc46143d-m8DbHtF>

- Grebel, J., Raffa, J. D., Lai, C., Kradjen, M., Kerr, T., Fischer, B., & Tyndall, M. W. (2009). Low uptake of treatment for hepatitis C virus infection in a large community-based study of inner-city residents. *Journal of Viral Hepatitis*, *16*(5), 52–358. doi:10.1111/j.1365893.2009. 01080.x
- Hulton, L. J. (2007). An evaluation of a school-based teenage pregnancy prevention program using a logic model framework. *Journal of School Nursing*, *23*(2), 104–110.
- Israel, G. D. (2010). Using logic models for program development (AEC 360). Gainesville, FL: University of South Florida, IFAS Extension. Retrieved from <http://edis.ifas.ufl.edu/wc041>.
- Jewett, A., Garg, A., Meyer, K., Wagner, L. D., Krauskopf, K., Brown, K. A., . . . Rein, D. B. (2015). Hepatitis C virus testing perspectives among primary care physicians in four large primary care settings. *Health Promotion Practice*, *16*(2), 256-263. doi
- Johnson, R.L., Blumen, H.E., & Ferro, C. (2015). The burden of hepatitis C virus disease in commercial and managed Medicaid populations. Retrieved from <http://californiahcvtaskforce.org/pdf/milliman-hcv-burden.pdf>
- Jorgensen, C., Lewis, C., & Liu, J. (2012). An analysis of hepatitis C virus-related public inquiries from health professionals: 2009-2010. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*, *55*(Suppl 1), S54-7.

- Joukar, F., Mansour-Ghanaei, F., Soati, F., & Meskinkhoda, P. (2012). Knowledge levels and attitudes of health care professionals toward patients with hepatitis c infection. *World Journal of Gastroenterology*, *18*(18), 2238-2244. doi:10.3748/wjg.v18.i18.2238.
- Katzman, J. G., Comerci, G., Boyle, J. F., Duhigg, D., Shelley, B., Olivas, C., . . . Arora, S. (2014). Innovative telementoring for pain management: Project ECHO Pain. *Journal of Community Medical Health Education Practice*, *34*(1), 68-75. doi:10.1002/chp.21210
- Linas, B. P., Hu, H., Barter, D. M., & Horberg, M. (2014). Hepatitis C screening trends in a large integrated health system. *The American Journal of Medicine*, *127*(5), 398-405. doi: 10.1016/j.amjmed.2014.01.012.
- Mahale, P., Torres, H. A., Kramer, J. R., Hwang, L., Li, R., Brown, E. L., & Engels, E. A. (2017). Hepatitis C virus infection and the risk of cancer among elderly US adults: A registry-based case-control study. *Cancer*, *123*(7),1202-1211.
- Masi, C., Hamlis, T., Davis, A., Bordenave, K., Brown, S., Perea, B., . . . Johnson, D. (2012). Using an established telehealth model to train urban primary care providers on hypertension management. *The Journal of Clinical Hypertension*, *14*(1) 45-50. doi:10.1111/j.1751-7176.2011. 00559.x
- McGowan, C. E., Monis, A., Bacon, B. R., Mallolas, J., Goncales, F. L., Goulis, I., . . . Fried, M. W. (2013). A Global view of hepatitis C: Physician knowledge, opinions, and perceived barriers to care. *Hepatology*, *57*(4), 1325-1332. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/hep.26246>

- McKinney, W.P. (2017). Assessing the evidence for the educational efficacy of webinars and related internet-based instruction. *Pedagogy in Health Promotion*, 3(1S), 47S-51S. doi: 10.1177/2373379917700876.
- Mitchell, A. E., Colvin, H. E., & Beasley, R. P. (2010). Institute of Medicine recommendations for the prevention and control of hepatitis B and C. *Hepatology*, 51(3), 729–733. doi:10.1002/hep.23561
- Mitruka, K., Thornton, K., Cusick, S., Orme, C., Moore, A., Manch, R.A., . . . Ward, J. W. (2014). Expanding primary care capacity to treat hepatitis C virus infection through an evidence-based care model — Arizona and Utah, 2012–2014. *Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report*, 63(18), 393-398. doi: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/24855148>
- Moore, A., & Manch, R. A. (2013). Synchronous cohorts: A novel variation to the Project ECHO approach to hepatitis C treatment. Presented at: 64th Annual Meeting of the American Association for the Study of Liver Diseases: The Liver Meeting 2013; November 1-5, 2013; Washington, DC. *Hepatology*, 58(Suppl S1), 208A-1309A.
- Moyer, V. A. (2013). Screening for hepatitis C virus infection in adults: U.S. Preventive Services Task Force Recommendation Statement. *Annals of Internal Medicine*, 159(5), 349-358. doi:10.7326/0003-4819-159-5-201309030-00672
- Naghdi, R., Seto, K., Klassen, C., Emokpare, D., Conway, B., Kelley, M., . . . Shah, H.M. (2017). A Hepatitis C educational needs assessment of Canadian healthcare providers. *Canadian Journal of Gastroenterology and Hepatology*, 2017(5324290), 1-10. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/5324290>

- National Academy of Sciences. (2017). Hepatitis and liver cancer: A national strategy for prevention and control of Hepatitis B and C. Retrieved from <http://www.nap.edu/catalog/12793.html>
- Peksen, Y., Canbaz, S., Leblebicioglu, H., Sunbul, M., Esen, S., & Sunter, A. (2004). Primary care physician's approach to diagnosis and treatment of hepatitis B and hepatitis C patients. *BMC Gastroenterology*, 4(3). doi:10.1186/1471-230X-4-3
- Renger, R., & Hurley, C. (2006). From theory to practice: Lessons learned in the application of the ATM approach to developing logic models. *Evaluation and Program Planning*, 29, 106– 119.
- Salgia, R. J., McCurdy, H., & Moseley, R. H. (2014). The educational impact of the specialty care access network-extension of community healthcare outcomes program. *Telemedicine and e-Health*, 20(11)1004-1008. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1089/tmj.2013.0302>
- Scott, J. D., Unruh, K. T, Catlin, M. C., Merrill, J. O, Tauben, D. J., & Rosenblatt, R. . . . Spacha, D. H. (2012). Project ECHO: A model for complex, chronic care in the Pacific Northwest region of the United States. *Journal of Telemedicine & Telecare*, 18(8), 481-484.
- Shehab, T. M., Sonnad, S. S., & Lok, A. S. (2001). Management of hepatitis C patients by primary care physicians in the USA: Results of a national survey. *Journal of Viral Hepatitis*, 8(5), 377-383. doi: 10.1046/j.1365-2893.2001.00310.x]

- Southern, W. N., Drainoni, M. L., Smith, B. D., McKee, C. L., Gifford, A. L., & Litwin, A. H. (2011). Hepatitis C testing practices and prevalence in a high-risk urban ambulatory care setting. *Journal of Viral Hepatitis*, *18*(7), 474-81. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2893.2010.01327.x.
- The University of New Mexico. (2018). *Project ECHO: A Revolution in Medical Education and Care Delivery*. Retrieved from <https://echo.unm.edu/>
- Thomson, M., Konerman, M. A., Choxi, M., & Lok, A.S. F. (2016). Primary care physician perspectives on hepatitis C management in the era of direct-acting antiviral therapy. *Digestive Diseases and Sciences*, *61*(12), 3460–3468. doi:10.1007/s10620-016-4097-2.
- Traphagan, T., Kucsera, J.V., & Kishi, K. (2010). Impact of class lecture webcasting on attendance and learning. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, *58*(1), 19–37.
- University of Kansas. (2018). Chapter 2. Other models for promoting community health and development » Section 1. Developing a logic model or theory of change. Retrieved from <https://ctb.ku.edu/en/table-of-contents/overview/models-for-community-health-and-development/logic-model-development/main>
- U.S. Department of Health and Human Services. (2017). The U.S. National Viral Hepatitis Action Plan for 2017-2020. Retrieved from <https://www.hhs.gov/sites/default/files/National%20Viral%20Hepatitis%20Action%20Plan%202017-2020.pdf>

- World Health Organization (WHO, 2016). Monitoring and evaluation for viral hepatitis B and C: Recommended indicators and framework. Retrieved from http://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/204790/9789241510288_eng.pdf;jsessionid=9CFB3124D0BED6A03FF20E5357D3709D?sequence=1
- World Health Organization (2017a). *Global hepatitis report, 2017*. Retrieved from <http://www.who.int/hepatitis/publications/global-hepatitis-report2017/en/>
- World Health Organization (2017b). Guidelines for the screening, care, and treatment of persons with chronic hepatitis C. Retrieved from <http://www.who.int/hepatitis/publications/hepatitis-c-guidelines-2016/en/>
- W. K. Kellogg Foundation. (2004). Logic model development guide. Battle Creek, MI: Author. Retrieved from <http://www.smartgivers.org/uploads/logicmodelguidepdf.pdf>.
- Younossi, Z. M., Boparai, N., Price, L. L., Kiwi, M. L., McCormick, M., & Guyatt, G. (2001). Health-related quality of life in chronic liver disease: The impact of type and severity of disease. *American Journal of Gastroenterology*, *96*(7), 2199-2205.
- Zaccagnini, M. E., & White, K. W. (2014). *The doctor of nursing practice essentials: A new model for advance practice nursing* (2nd ed.). Sudbury, MA: Jones and Bartlett.

APPENDIX A**RECRUITMENT E-MAIL, THANK-YOU, AND REMINDER**

FROM: [REDACTED] via SurveyMonkey
DATE: Tuesday, February 12, 2019 1:52 PM
SENT TO: 1 recipient
SUBJECT: Invitation to Complete Hepatitis-C hybrid SCAN-ECHO Educational Series QI Study Survey
MESSAGE:

**HEP-C PATIENT MANAGEMENT
COMPETENCY Tool_Post SCAN-ECHO
Provider Evaluation*Adapted with
approved permission from the NUTCOMP
Tool (Ball & Leveritt, 2015).**

Hello.

My name is Esther M. Robinson, and I am a Doctorate of Nursing Practice (DNP) student from California State University, Los Angeles working with Dr. Debika Bhattacharya of the Liver Clinic at the VA Greater LA Healthcare System (VAGLAHS). My faculty adviser is Elizabeth Winokur, Ph.D., RN. We are conducting a Quality Improvement (QI) study about the Hepatitis-C hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational series that you participated in since it began in 2016. The aim is to evaluate the extent to which the participation improved your skills in the management of Hepatitis-C patients. I am emailing to ask if you could please take about 5-10 minutes of your time to complete a survey for this project. Participation is entirely voluntary, and your responses will be anonymous.

If you are interested, please click here for the survey and additional information to complete it on the SurveyMonkey site. There is no additional consent form to sign because by clicking on the link to complete the survey, you have consented to participation. If you have questions at any time about the project or the procedures, you may contact my VAGLAHS project supervisor, Dr. Debika Bhattacharya via phone at [REDACTED] or email at [REDACTED] or [REDACTED]. You may also contact my faculty adviser Dr. Elizabeth Winokur at [REDACTED] or e-mail at [REDACTED]. You may also contact me via phone at [REDACTED] or e-mail at [REDACTED].

Thankfully,
Esther M. Robinson
DNP Student

[Begin Survey](#)

Sent thank you

FROM: [REDACTED] SurveyMonkey
DATE: Wednesday, February 20, 2019 10:34 AM
SENT TO: 3 recipients
SUBJECT: Thank you for taking our survey!
MESSAGE:

HEP-C PATIENT MANAGEMENT COMPETENCY
Tool_Post SCAN-ECHO Provider
evaluation* Adapted with approved permission from
the NUTCOMP Tool (Ball & Leveritt, 2015).

Thank you so very much for taking our recent survey. We appreciate your valuable feedback!

REMINDER E-MAILS: First, second and final

Hello.

I am following up on the e-mail you previously received about the QI study about the 2016 Hepatitis-C hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational and management series you may have taken part in. Please find some time to complete the online survey if you have not already done so; it takes about 10 minutes.

If you have any additional questions, please do not hesitate to contact me at [REDACTED].

Thank you very much for your time.

Thankfully,
Esther M. Robinson
Cal State Fullerton, DNP Student

Sent reminder

- **FROM:** [REDACTED] via SurveyMonkey
- **DATE:** Friday, February 22, 2019 12:00 AM
- **SENT TO:** 22 recipients
- **SUBJECT:** Reminder: We value your feedback!
- **MESSAGE:**

HEP-C PATIENT MANAGEMENT
COMPETENCY Tool_Post SCAN-
ECHO Provider
Evaluation*Adapted with approved
permission from the NUTCOMP
Tool (Ball & Leveritt, 2015).

Greetings!

We recently contacted you about the Hep-C Patient Management Competency Post SCAN-ECHO Provider Evaluation survey, but haven't received your responses. We'd really appreciate your participation.

Click the button below to start or continue the survey. Thank you so very much for your time!

[Begin Survey](#)

APPENDIX B

**SURVEYMONKEY WEBSITE: PROJECT PARTICIPANT
INFORMATION SHEET**

HEP-C PATIENT MANAGEMENT COMPETENCY Tool Post SCAN-ECHO Provider Evaluation
*Adapted with approved permission from the NUTCOMP Tool (Ball & Leveritt, 2015).

1. PROJECT PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

To Project Participant:

You are invited to take part in a Quality Improvement (QI) study conducted by Esther M. Robinson, NP, MSN, MPH/DNP student, California State University, Los Angeles; Debika Bhattacharya, MD, MSc of the Division of Infectious Diseases UCLA CARE Center and the VA Greater Los Angeles Healthcare System (VAGLAHS); and Elizabeth Winokur, PhD, RN, Assistant Professor, California State University, Los Angeles. The purpose of the project is to evaluate the impact of the hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational and management series on perceptions of improved competency in the identification, screening, diagnosis, treatment and ongoing management of patients with Hepatitis- C. You were selected to participate in this project because you were involved in the hybrid SCAN- ECHO educational and management series that began in 2016.

You are asked to complete a survey through this Survey Monkey site that should take less than 10 minutes. You can choose not to answer any questions without penalty. There is an anticipated risk of potential loss of confidentiality. There is also the risk of possible constraints on your time to complete the survey.

We will not be requesting nor collecting any identifying information such as IP addresses from Survey Monkey. No individual participant information will be obtained or be available. Reports resulting from this study will not identify you as a participant. All information gathered in this project is de-identified and results will be reported only in general or aggregated methods.

If you have questions at any time about the project or the procedures, you may contact my VAGLAHS project supervisor, Dr. Debika Bhattacharya via phone at [REDACTED] or email at [REDACTED] or [REDACTED]. You may also contact my faculty adviser Dr. Elizabeth Winokur at [REDACTED] or e-mail at [REDACTED]. You may also contact me via phone at [REDACTED] or e-mail at [REDACTED].

By completing the survey, you indicate that you have read the form and agreed voluntarily to participate in the project. If you choose not to take part, there will be no penalty or loss of benefits to which you are entitled. If you agree to take part, you are free to withdraw from it at any time. Likewise, no penalty or loss of benefits to which you are otherwise entitled will occur.

THIS PROJECT HAS BEEN DETERMINED TO BE EXEMPT FROM REVIEW AND APPROVAL BY THE CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LOS ANGELES INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD FOR THE PROTECTION OF HUMAN SUBJECTS IN RESEARCH.

APPENDIX C

LETTER TO REQUEST PERMISSION TO ADAPT THE NUTCOMP TOOL
FOR USE WITH GRANTED APPROVAL

Dear Esther,

Yes you are welcome to adapt the survey pending that you cite the original work in your publication. I have attached some documents you may find useful.

Wishing you all the best for your project.

Kindest Regards,
Lauren

Dr Lauren Ball

NHMRC Research Fellow in Primary Care

Co-Lead, Patient-Centred Health Services

Menzies Health Institute Queensland

Adjunct Senior Research Fellow, UQ-MRI Centre for Health System Reform and Innovation

G01 2.05A, Griffith University,

Gold Coast, Australia

Want to know more about me? Check out my website:

www.dr Lauren Ball.com

Ph: 0413031470

Twitter: [@laurenball01](https://twitter.com/laurenball01)

LinkedIn: [Lauren Ball](#)

From: **Esther Robinson** <[REDACTED]>

Date: Sun, Apr 15, 2018 at 11:28 PM

Subject: Request for Permission to Adapt the NUTCOMP Tool to Use for a DNP Final Project

To: [REDACTED]

Dear Dr. Ball,

Greetings! I'm a Doctor of Nursing (DNP) student exploring validated tools available to measure healthcare provider competency. I came across the NUTCOMP Tool and would be honored to adapt it to use for my project. I'm trying to evaluate self-perceived improved competency by a group of primary care providers in the care of HCV patients.

Respectfully,
Esther M. Robinson

APPENDIX D

HEP-C PATIENT MANAGEMENT COMPETENCY TOOL

<i>Section One: Confidence in Knowledge about Hepatitis-C and Chronic Disease</i>					
<i>Please rate how more confident you are in your knowledge of . . .</i>	Not at all Confident (1 point)	Not so Confident (2 points)	Somewhat Confident (3 points)	Very Confident (4 points)	Extremely Confident (5 points)
1. How different population groups are at higher risk for development of Hepatitis-C	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. How risk factors influence the development and management of chronic Hepatitis-C	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. The USPSTF guidelines for the management of chronic HCV infected patients	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Pharmacology and pharmacotherapeutics of medications used for Hepatitis-C treatment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. The most recently published peer-reviewed evidence regarding Hepatitis-C and chronic disease care management	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Section Two: Confidence in Hepatitis-C Management Skills</i>					
<i>Please rate how more confident you are in your ability to . . .</i>	Not at all Confident (1 point)	Not so Confident (2 points)	Somewhat Confident (3 points)	Very Confident (4 points)	Extrem Confid (5 poi
1. Interpret lab data about Viral Hepatitis C Antibody Screen; Viral Hepatitis C RNA by PCR; Hepatitis C Virus Genotype	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Use the USPSTF guidelines to evaluate the appropriateness of an individual's HCV screening against risk factors	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Evaluate HCV Infected patients' candidacy for treatment, including the evaluation of patient factors (liver disease staging, psychosocial determinants) and viral factors (HCV genotype, treatment-experience) importance in assessing the HCV treatment regimen	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Section Three: Attitudes Towards HCV Patient Care					
Please rate your agreement with the following statements:	Strongly Disagree (1 point)	Disagree (2 points)	Neither Agree nor Disagree (3 points)	Agree (4 points)	Strongly Agree (5 points)
1. It is important that all individuals born between 1945-1965 be screened for HCV regardless of age, race and risk factors	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. It is important that I take every opportunity possible to encourage my patients/clients to avoid HCV risk behaviors	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Encouraging my patients/clients to avoid HCV risky behaviors is an effective use of my professional time	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. It is important that I refer my patients/ clients to other health care professionals if I am unable to meet their HCV-related care management needs	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Section Four: Impact of Previous SCAN-ECHO Educational Series (not scored)

4. How has your participation in the 2016 Hepatitis-C hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational and management series improved your management of HCV types of patients?

5. How many sessions of the 2016 Hepatitis-C hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational and management series did you take part in?

- a. 0
- b. 1
- c. 2
- d. ≥ 3
- e. Decline to answer

6. What was the primary motivation for your participation in the 2016 Hepatitis-C hybrid SCAN-ECHO educational and management series for HCV?

- a. To gain new knowledge about identifying, screening, diagnosing, treating, and providing ongoing management for HCV patients.
- b. To increase my knowledge and improve my experience with identifying, screening, diagnosing, treating, and providing ongoing management for HCV patients.
- c. I was mandated by leadership to participate.
- d. I have no primary reason other than curiosity.

Section Five: Demographic Information

1. What is your profession? (Please check any that apply)
 - a. Medical Doctor
 - b. Nurse Practitioner
 - c. Clinical Pharmacist
 - d. Mental Health Provider (i.e., psychiatrist, psychologist)
 - e. Other (Please specify _____)

2. How many years have you been working in this profession? _____ Years

3. What is your gender?
 - a. Male
 - b. Female
 - c. Decline to answer

4. What is your ethnicity?
 - a. White/Caucasian
 - b. Black/African-American
 - c. Hispanic/Latino
 - d. Asian/Asian American
 - e. Native American/Alaska native
 - f. Native Hawaiian/Other Pacific Islander
 - g. Another race
 - h. Decline to answer

5. What is your age range?
 - a. 24 years or younger
 - b. 25-34 years
 - c. 35-44 years
 - d. 45-54 years
 - e. 55-64 years
 - f. 65 years or older
 - g. Prefer not to say

*Adapted with approved permission from the NUTCOMP Tool (Ball & Leveritt, 2015)

APPENDIX E

IRB APPROVAL LETTERS

From: Corey, Elizabeth L
Sent: Tuesday, August 07, 2018 7:09 PM
To: Robinson, Esther M [REDACTED]
Cc: Roch, Margaret A. [REDACTED]
Subject: SCAN - ECHO - HRPP Determination

Attached, please find the signed form 00 and memo of the HRPP determination that the proposed work is Quality Improvement/not research.

Please note that this is the only communication you will receive regarding this determination. The PCC # will be withdrawn from the research inventory and will not be tracked as a research project. SEE BELOW Please keep in touch regarding any developments within the project and notify me if there is any re-use of this QI data for any other purpose, in order that I can instruct you regarding an IRB application.

Thank you for your patience regarding this process. – liz

Project ID	Proj #				
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PCC Submissions					
Principal Investigator	PCC#	Log In	Campus	ProjectId	Proj #
Robinson, Esther M., MSN, MPH	2018-060566	06/13/2018	WLA		
Project Title				Withdrawn on 08/07/2018	
Evaluating Provider Perceived Improved Hepatitis-C Management Skills with the SCAN-ECHO Educational Series					
Type of Submission	<input type="checkbox"/> IACUC	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> IRB	VACO #	Fund #	Ad
New	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SRS	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D		0000	
Sponsor's Protocol #	Version	Grant #	Co-Principal Investigators		
Coordinator/Contact				Catgry	
Approved	Sign Off		Notes		
IRB	08/07/2018	08/07/2018	QI_Determination_NoRDC_needed		
SRS			Form 00 - IRB DeterminationRSS		
IACUC					
R&D					
Committee	Received	Comment			

Elizabeth L. Corey, Ph.D.

HRPP Administrator

U.S. Department of Veterans Affairs

Research and Development/Research Service – IRB

VA Greater Los Angeles Healthcare System

11301 Wilshire Blvd., Bldg. 114 Room 326-A-1 | Los Angeles, CA 90073

Phone: ~~(310) 268-3080 (M-F)~~/~~Sepulveda (818) 891-7711x 38025 (Thursdays)~~

Fax: (310) 268-4856

CONFIDENTIALITY NOTICE: *This e-mail is intended only for the person or entity to which it is addressed, and may contain information that is privileged, confidential, or otherwise protected from disclosure. Dissemination, distribution, printing or copying of this e-mail or the information herein by anyone other than the intended recipient is prohibited. If you have received this e-mail in error, please notify the sender by reply e-mail, and destroy the original message and all copies. Thank you.*

Office Memorandum

DATE: December 13, 2018

TO: Elizabeth Winokur, PhD
FROM: California State University, Los Angeles
(Cal State LA) IRB

PROJECT TITLE: [1059693-1] Evaluating Provider Perceived Improved Hepatitis-C Management Skills with the SCAN-ECHO Educational Series

REFERENCE #: 17-259X
SUBMISSION TYPE: New Project

ACTION: DETERMINATION OF EXEMPT STATUS

DECISION DATE: December 13, 2018

REVIEW CATEGORY: Exemption category # 2

Thank you for your submission of New Project materials for this project. The California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB has determined that this project is EXEMPT FROM IRB REVIEW according to federal regulations. We will retain a copy of this correspondence within our records.

IF ANY CHANGES ARE MADE TO THE METHODS AND PROCEDURES DESCRIBED IN THIS PROTOCOL, YOU MUST SUBMIT ANOTHER APPLICATION SO THAT THE PROJECT MAY BE REEVALUATED FOR EXEMPTION FROM IRB REVIEW.

If you have any questions, please contact [Elia Amaro at irb@calstatela.edu](mailto:Elia.Amaro@calstatela.edu) or irb@calstatela.edu. Please include your project title and reference number in all correspondence with this committee.

APPENDIX F

TABLE OF EVIDENCE

Table 1

Hepatitis-C Prevalence, Incidence, and Screening by Primary Care Providers

Purpose	Design/Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key Findings	Conclusions	Limitations/Notes
To estimate the cost-effectiveness of birth-cohort HCV screening by PCPs (Rein et al., 2017)	Cost-effectiveness simulation Variables: Costs, pts	NHANES data 2001-2006 U.S. adults born 1945-1965 w/ ≥ 1 PCP visit/yr.	One-time antibody testing of 1945–1965 birth cohort. # of cases ID'd & Txd achieving sustained viral response; liver dx & HCV-related deaths; medical & productivity costs; QALYs & ICER.	Birth-cohort screening ID'd 808, 580 more cases of chronic HCV infection @ a screening cost of \$2874/case ID'd.	Birth-cohort screening for HCV in primary care settings = cost-effective.	Limitations: Scarcity of actual data on screening & direct-acting antiviral Tx in QD clinical settings. Study superbly highlights the cost-effectiveness of prompt patient screenings for HCV.
To evaluate relationship between HCV infection and development of cancers among US elders (Mahale, Torres, Kramer, Hwang, Li, Brown, & Engels, 2017)	Registry-based case control study DV = HCV IDV = Cancer prevalence.	1,623,538 persons who had cancer 1 st ID'd via SEER registries 1993-2011 (cases). 200,000 randomly selected cancer-free individuals matched to cases on age, sex, race, and calendar year (control group).	HCV prevalence – Medicare claims reviewed using ICD-9 codes	Control group had lower HCV prevalence than did those with cancer (0.5% vs. 0.7%). HCV associated w/ many types of cancer esp. liver (aOR = 31.4),	Results mean HCV plays a role in certain cancers.	Limitations: Study population of elderly makes generalization to younger group difficult. Study illustrates PCPs need to closely screen patients for HCV across age groups.

Purpose	Design/Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key Findings	Conclusions	Limitations/Notes
				bile ducts (aOR = 3.4)		
To evaluate the extent of HCV screening on pt care in five primary care settings using linkage-to-care concept. (Coyle, Kwakwa & Viner, 2016)	PCP-initiated vs. MA-initiated testing for HCV. Opt-out & linkage-to-care model used	4,207 tested Five established urban primary centers in Philadelphia	MAs ID'd pts for screening & informed of planned testing unless refuse HCV RNA testing	11.6% (488) patients anti-HCV (+) tested 7.4% (313) patients HCV RNA (+) Adults 50-69 yrs. (10.7%) w/ highest rates of active infection	Using Medical Assistants to ID patients for HCV screening helpful in the primary care Model used shows how linkage to care can be integrated into primary care.	Limitations: Model's used w/in a pre-existing pt group. # of pts who rec'd HCV Tx @ one of the settings not representative of actual # of HCV pts The fact that those in the birth-cohort (50-69 yrs. of age) group had the highest rate of infection was of significance.
To evaluate views R/T HCV testing based on CDC birth-cohort guidelines (Jewett et al., 2015)	Qualitative	19 participants; 6 PCPs, 5 hospital administrators & 8 Hepatologists 4 well-known established US health-care systems	Interviews – Approx. 45-min semi-structured interviews of PCPs, administrators, & Hepatologists PCPs interviewed R/T guidelines stressing their role in HCV testing. Administrators interviewed R/T their role in stressing PCP	PCPs primarily focused efforts on screening those with H/O IVDA, tattoos, risky sexual behaviors, etc. Administrators see the use of various educational means (i.e., grand rounds, webinars, etc.) to educate PCPs. Hepatologists showed concerns R/T	Birth-cohort HCV screening much better means to ID high-risk pts Augmenting PCP knowledge-base R/T need for HCV-focused screening best achieved by ongoing education	Limitations: Participants aware of HCV knowledge ??? ahead of time & also aware that CDC official would be present during the interview. Also, the setting of large urban systems affects generalizability to all settings. Relevant study highlight -ing fact that PCPs don't routinely test pts for HCV.

Purpose	Design/Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key Findings	Conclusions	Limitations/Notes
			adherence to guidelines Hepatologists interviewed R/T need to comprehend barriers to referrals from PCPs	failed screening by PCPs; pt usually referred after (+) HCV antibody test result.		
To describe HCV screening patterns in primary care settings w/in the KPMAS health system (Linan, Hu, Barter & Horberg, 2014)	Descriptive Jan'03-Dec'12 HCV trends of screening. Chart reviews	444,594 patients met criteria Large healthcare system – Mid-Atlantic States	Demographics (e.g., DOB, gender, race, etc.); H/O drug use; & lab tests	15.8% of pts have ever been screened for HCV OB/Gyn (31.7%) & Adult PCP (44.2%) screened the most patients Only 14.4% of birth-cohort group members screened though the group is @ highest risk for HCV infection HCV (+) rates highest amongst birth-cohort groups; 20.6% combined gender Younger-aged patients more likely to be screened	HCV screening practices not ideal – need exists for providers to screen those among the birth-cohort group due to highest HCV rates.	Limitations: Data based on lab results & visits w/in a healthcare system.

Purpose	Design/Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key Findings	Conclusions	Limitations/Notes
To assess the cost-effectiveness of one-time risk assessment & screening to ID undxd 40–74-year-olds given newly available hep-C tx (Liu et al., 2013).	<p>Markov model used to analyze data</p> <p>Attempted to answer these ???:</p> <p>-Can using risk assessment to ID HCV pts improve costs & benefits of screening?</p> <p>-Is later dx mgmt., HCV tx uptake, & tx type affected by the cost-effectiveness of HCV screening?</p>	<p>Variables: Costs, pts</p> <p>NHANES data (2001–2008)</p>	<p><i>Cohorts</i>;</p> <p>stratified by age, sex, race, risk hx, HCV infection status, HCV genotype, tx eligibility, IL-28B genotype, & initial liver fibrosis stage.</p> <p><i>Screening & tx</i>;</p> <p>No screening vs. risk-factor guided vs. birth-cohort</p> <p><i>HCV Natural Hx</i>; tx arrests dx progress</p> <p><i>Risk factors & HCV prevalence</i>;</p> <p>Mortality rates; age, sex, race, risk status, & HCV infection calculated</p> <p><i>Risk Assessment</i>;</p> <p>Tx eligibility; co-morbidities (i.e., medical & mental illness, substance abuse, etc.) affect this factor</p> <p><i>Tx uptake & ongoing monitoring</i>;</p> <p>eval'd</p>	<p>Compared to no screening, risk-factor guided & birth-cohort screening for 50-yr-olds gained 0.7-3.5 QALD & cost \$168 to \$568/ person.</p> <p>Presumptuous tx w/ triple therapy, screening all persons aged 40–64 years costs less than \$ 100,000/ QALY</p>	<p>Along with giving birth-cohort screening, HCV policies ought to focus on guaranteeing that screen-detected persons receive prompt HCV tx & high-quality care</p>	<p>Limitations:</p> <p>Analysis of NHANES data to estimate HCV prevalence stratified by sex, race, & risk-factor status focused on small sample sizes.</p> <p>Didn't include people w/ HIV or HBV co-infections</p> <p>R/T the difficulties of the 2 dz & clinical challenges of safe & effective tx both. Despite small sample size & lack of inclusion of HIV & HBV pts & other limitations, study excellently highlights the cost-effectiveness of prompt pt screenings for HCV.</p>

Purpose	Design/Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key Findings	Conclusions	Limitations/Notes
			<p>immediate vs. delayed care <i>HRQL</i>; chronic HCV infection impact <i>Costs</i>; screening, time, tx factors considered <i>Cost-effectiveness</i>; QALYs & lifetime costs mainly</p>			
<p>To find out the actual HCV testing rate among pts w/ HCV risk factors (Almario, Vega, Trooskin & Navarro, 2012).</p>	<p>Attempted to ID variables predictive of testing</p> <p>Prospective cohort study</p> <p>Questionnaire</p>	<p>578 pts acknowledged (+) HCV risk factor</p> <p>4 urban primary care clinics</p>	<p>At 1st visit, pts were provided questionnaire listing HCV risk factors.</p> <p>Instructed to check 'yes' or 'no' to show presence or absence of a risk factor. Then form given to PCP.</p>	<p>Only 8% (46/578) tested for HCV w/in 2 mons of their 1st visit.</p> <p>Of those tested, 11% (5/46) had a (+) a positive HCV antibody result.</p>	<p>92% of pts w/ an HCV risk factor were not tested for HCV in the primary care setting</p> <p>More efforts to improve such rates are called for.</p>	<p>Limitations: Self-report of risk-factors may have affected the internal validity of data.</p>
<p>To study HCV testing practices to learn pt features linked w/ HCV testing & (+) results, & to estimate HCV infection prevalence in a high-</p>	<p>Hepatitis-C Assessment and Testing Project (HepCAT)</p> <p>Serial cross-sectional study of HCV screening approaches</p>	<p>All pts w/ clinic visits to Montefiore Medical Center; NY</p> <p>Pts ≥ 18 yrs. old having a primary care visit to one of the 3 participating clinics</p>	<p>Pt demographics (i.e., age, race/ethnicity, etc.) & clinical features (i.e., HCV test status hx, psych hx, etc.).</p>	<p>9,579 pts data studied</p> <p>Anti-HCV prevalence btwn the 3803 (39.7%) pts in this sample tested was 11.5%</p>	<p>↑ projected HCV infection rates in a high-risk urban pt group w/ a high prevalence of risk factors.</p>	<p>Limitations: Not all pts were tested for anti-HCV</p> <p>EMR use for data gathering affected the extent of data capture of all risk factors for HCV infection for each pt</p>

Purpose	Design/Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key Findings	Conclusions	Limitations/Notes
risk urban population (Southern et al., 2011)	Retrospective EMR review	01/01/08 -02/29/08				No consideration given to historical association btwn risk factors & HCV tests
To understand family physician HCV practice patterns, knowledge, beliefs, & attitudes (Clark, Yawn, Galliher, Temte, & Hincker, 2005).	Survey; 30-item March-June 2003 - Pilot study of the survey in March @ Convention - Surveys mailed in June 2003	1,200 randomly selected PCPs from AAFP Membership - 634 (53%) surveys completed & returned	HCV practice patterns, knowledge, beliefs, & attitudes	94% reported having at @ least 1-HCV pt w/in their practice, Most felt physicians should screen (94%), dx (98%), provide tx & ongoing mgmt (69%) for HCV pts.	PCPs know how to ID ↑-risk persons & test for HCV. Most PCPs favor HCV pt referral to specialists for work↑ & tx but face freq. associated barriers.	Limitation: Self-report of data affected internal validity. Multiple-choice response options affected the extent of responses. Results may not be generalizable to non-AAFP members or other PCPs. Nevertheless, the study highlighted the HCV knowledge-deficit.
To appraise HCV prevalence rates & infection risk factors among a veteran group (Dominitz et al., 2005).	Two-staged cluster sample Cross-sectional population-based 20/145 VAMCs randomly selected based on size of pt population.	N= 4,000 (3,184,687 initial pool) Veterans 1 st mailed invitation letters after IRB approval of study 2 nd letter w/ phone calls if NO response Data collected @ participant's home or preferred location.	Blood tests for anti-HCV antibody done.	86/4,000 (2.2%) unable to give consent R/T death, imprisoned or military deployment & so replaced Others (93 = 2.3%) unable to give consent R/T death, imprisoned or	VHA should focus efforts on HCV prevention, screening, counseling & Tx R/T ↑ veteran prevalence	Limitations: Non-participation by veterans lost to F/U Study illustrates the fact that VAMC pts are w/ higher HCV rates than the general population.

Purpose	Design/Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key Findings	Conclusions	Limitations/Notes
				military deployment but not replaced		
				52/1,288 tested HCV (+).		
				4% past HCV (+) antibody prevalence noted among participants		

Notes. @ = At; aOR = Adjusted Odds Ratio; Btwn = Between; Birth-cohort group = Born between 1945-1965; DOB = Date of Birth; Dx = Disease; EMR = Electronic Medical Record; HCV= Hepatitis-C Virus; HRQL = Health-Related Quality of Life; H/O: History of; NHANES = National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey; ICER = Incremental cost-effectiveness ratio; ICD-9 = International Classification of Diseases, version 9; ID/ID'd = Identify/Identified; IRB = Institutional Review Board; IVDA = IV Drug Abuse; KPMAS = Kaiser Permanente Mid-Atlantic States; Medical Assistants = Medical Assistants; NY = New York; OB/Gyn = Obstetrics & Gynecology; OR Tech = Operating Room Technicians; PCPs = Primary Care Providers; QALDs = Quality adjusted life-days; QALYs = Quality-adjusted life-years; QD = Everyday; RNA = Ribonucleic Acid; R/T = Related to; SEER = Surveillance, Epidemiology, and End Results; Tx = Treatment; U.S. = United States; undxd = Undiagnosed; Vs. = Versus; W/ = With; Yr. = Year

Table 2

Hepatitis-C Knowledge, Attitudes and Practice Patterns Among PCPs

Purpose	Design/ Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key findings	Author Conclusions	Limitations/Notes
To appraise PCP HCV current practice patterns &/or willingness to improve self-competency (Falade-Nwulia et al., 2016).	Quantitative Internet-based survey; 42-item Current practice patterns &/or willingness to improve self-competency.	270 PCPs from community clinics linked to large academic center & 4 FQHCs.	PCP demographics, clinical practice site & willingness to manage HCV pts	129 (48%) PCPs responded -12 (10%) Txd @ least 1 HCV pt in the earlier yr. -Only 22% agreed w/ need for HCV Tx by PCP though 84% interested in ↑ HCV training -↑ # of HCV pts under care = ↑ willingness to give care	Data shows HCV pt mgmt. by PCPs w/ ↑ pre-existing # of these pts on their panel is best approach to 1 st training efforts.	Limitations: Small sample size & urban setting. Use of questionnaire forced participants to respond to ??? as though they'd pre-existing general HCV knowledge.
To assess PCP knowledge & views on CHC screening, dx, referral, & tx. (Thomson, Konerman, Choxi & Lok, 2016).	Descriptive Anonymous survey	PCPs engaged in routine OP care @ a hosp Eighty (36 %) eligible PCPs completed the survey	More than ½ = females (60 %) aged 36–50 (55 %) Family = (44 %) Internal medicine = (49 %)	While most PCPs surveyed accurately, ID'd high-risk HCV pts, 19%, & 45% were unable to ID the birth-cohort group & HD pts respectively as higher risk populations	Efforts to address HCV screening barriers & expand tx into OP care areas are required to maximize access to & use of tx cures.	Limitations: PCP practice patterns influenced by specialty & Veterans Affairs Hospital affiliation.
To ID global PCP HCV practice patterns perceived barriers to care,	Mixed-mode survey study Survey; 214-items	697 physicians from 29 countries December 2010	Perceived barriers to care, knowledge, and opinions	100% item response rate Pt-level barriers seen	Barriers to HCV tx vary world-wide, yet pt-level factors viewed	Limitation: Response rate not representative of all providers.

Purpose	Design/ Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key findings	Author Conclusions	Limitations/Notes
knowledge, and opinions (McGowan et al., 2013).	Multidisciplinary HCV providers			as most noteworthy, including fear of S/E & concerns R/T tx duration & cost Central & Eastern European physicians cited govt. interference as barriers to care	as most important by providers. Energies should be directed @ improving awareness, education, & specialist availability.	Grouping of results affected generalizability R/T potential differences between providers in each country Study did an excellent job reflecting provider HCV-related competency issues across the globe.
To learn about the knowledge levels & attitudes of healthcare providers toward pts w/ HCV infection (Joukar, Mansour-Ghanaei, Soati, & Meskinkhoda, 2012)	Cross-sectional study Questionnaire	Guilan, a northern Iranian province. 239 health care professionals; nurses, doctors, & OR Techs	Demographics, knowledge levels, & attitudes toward Hepatitis C pts	Mean \pm SD knowledge score = 17.43 ± 2.65 (from a total of 22). 51.9% of the participants attained scores higher than the mean. Noteworthy association btwn know-ledge score & age ($P = 0.001$), gender ($P = 0.0001$), profession ($P = 0.0001$), & education ($P = 0.027$).	Biased attitudes aren't uncommon among health care providers toward Hepatitis C pts. Thus, it's crucial to expand their knowledge level & attitude toward the illness.	Limitations: Inability to confirm self-reported behavior against actual clinical behavior. Self-reported responses may not reflect responders' actual attitudes.

Purpose	Design/ Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key findings	Author Conclusions	Limitations/Notes
				<p>Also, noteworthy association btwn attitude level & age ($P = 0.002$), gender ($P = 0.0001$), profession ($P = 0.0001$), & education ($P = 0.035$).</p> <p>Doctors were suggestively more knowledgeable & displayed more (+) positive attitudes.</p> <p>(+) link btwn knowledge & attitude scores ($P = 0.02$).</p>		
To examine family physicians' know-ledge, attitudes & practices linked w/ HCV infection care provision (Cox et al., 2011)	Self-administered survey	749 members of the CFPC	Knowledge, attitudes & behaviors about HCV infection screening & care provision	Family physicians providing basic–advanced HCV tended to be older, practiced in a rural area, have pts w/ H/O IVDA in their practice & have higher levels of knowledge R/T the initial assessment (OR=1.77; 95% CI= 1.23–2.54) & tx of HCV (OR=1.74; 95% CI=1.24–2.43).	Educational strategies ought to be aimed @ physicians (i.e., family practitioners) least involved in HCV care provision working in inner-city areas & those not directly caring for IVDA pts.	Limitation: Self-reported responses may not reflect responders' actual attitudes.

Purpose	Design/ Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key findings	Author Conclusions	Limitations/Notes
					<p>Training & CME curricula aimed @ changing family physicians' attitudes about HCV care provision by encouraging their roles as vital could be the key.</p> <p>This focused shift could help to alleviate the drain on experts (i.e., Hepatologists) & lead to better access to HCV infection tx.</p>	
To describes a content analysis of e-mail inquiries sent to CDC's public inquiry system, CDC-INFO. (Jorgensen et al., 2012).	Content analysis	657 e-mail inquiries from the 2-year period (1 January 2009 through 31 December 2010)	E-mail inquiry coded by type of Hepatitis virus (HAV, HBV, HCV, Hepatitis D virus, and Hepatitis E virus) and type of info seeker (professional, public, or other). ??? asked assigned to one of 9 categories: transmission, serology, prevention, diagnosis, treatment/healthcare, legal/policy, blood	87 inquiries analyzed for 2009–2010, 37% from health professionals, and 63% from the public	Some knowledge and awareness about HCV is lacking among some health professionals	<p>Limitation: Sample embodies health professionals independently using the CDC-INFO system</p> <p>Some individual topic sample sizes small R/T lg. # of main topics.</p>

Purpose	Design/ Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key findings	Author Conclusions	Limitations/Notes
			donation, general statistics, or other.			
To examine factors affecting pt HCV development & related practice patterns by PCPs (Grebely et al., 2009)	Cohort study	2913 pts Community-based inner-city clinics in Vancouver, Canada. Jan'03 to June'04	HIV and HCV status Rxs for HCV	73% saw \leq 5 pts the earlier year, & 44% reported no experience with HCV tx. Only $\frac{1}{2}$ of the pts were referred to liver disease specialists	Enormously low rates of HCV tx start & very limited success, even w/ a high prevalence of HCV infection in this significant community-based cohort of inner-city residents w/ access to universal healthcare.	Limitation: Inner-city pt population; poor adherence to POC tx regimen

Note. $\frac{1}{2}$ = Half; # = Number; % = Percent; ??? = Questions; CDC-INFO = Centers for Disease Control & Prevention- Information; CHC = Chronic Hepatitis C; CI = Confidence Interval; CFPC = College of Family Physicians of Canada; CME = Continuing Medical Education; Dx = Diagnosis; FQHCs = Federally Qualified Health Centers; HAV = Hepatitis A Virus; HBV = Hepatitis B Virus; HCV= Hepatitis-C Virus; HD = Hemodialysis; H/O = History of; Hosp. = Hospital; ID/ID'd = Identify/identified; IVDA = Intravenous Drug Abuse; Lg. = Large; OP = Outpatient; OR = Odds Ratio; Pts = Patients; POC = Plan of Care; Rx = Prescriptions; R/T = Related to; Tx = Treatment

Table 3
Hepatitis-C Patient Treatment and Management Patterns and Competency among Providers

Purpose	Design/Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key findings	Author Conclusions	Limitations/Notes
To ascertain the value of HCV tx autonomously provided by NPs, PCPs, or specialist physicians using DAA therapy (Kattakuzhy et al. 2017).	Nonrandomized, open-label clinical trial initiated in 2015. Pts assigned to 1 of 5 NPs, 5 PCPs, or 6 specialists. Providers rec'd matching 3-hour training session based on guidelines. Pts rec'd tx w/ ledipasvir–sofosbuvir provided on site per U.S. FDA labeling requirements.	600 pts 13 FQHCs in the DC area	SVR	516 pts attained SVR (86% response rate) Response rates similar across the 3 provider types: - NPs, 89.3% (CI, 83.3% to 93.8%); - PCPs, 86.9% (CI, 80.6% to 91.7%); - Specialists, 83.8% (CI, 79.0% to 87.8%). Non-SVR R/T pt loss to F/U.	Data shows that w/ proper training HCV pt mgmt. by PCPs including NPs just as safe & reliable as specialist care.	Limitations: Non-randomized pt assignment; probable referral bias. The study did an excellent job of showing that w/ proper training PCPs including NPs could safely manage HCV pts.

Notes. CDC-INFO = Centers for Disease Control and Prevention-INFO; DAA= Direct-acting antiviral; DC = District of Columbia; FQHCs = Federally Qualified Health Centers; FDA = Food and Drug Administration; F/U = follow-up; Hr = Hour; HCV= Hepatitis-C Virus; NPs = Nurse practitioners; PCPs = Primary care physicians/providers; Pts = Patients; SVR = Sustained virologic response; Tx/tx = Treatment; U.S. = United States

Table 4
Educational Strategies to Augment Primary Care Providers Hepatitis-C Competency

Purpose	Design/Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key findings	Author Conclusions	Limitations/Notes
To describe the effective use of ECHO to augment PCP HCV competency (Mitruka et al., 2014).	Descriptive. Videoconferencing technology. Sept 30, 2012, to Feb 28, 2014.	ECHO programs in Utah & Arizona Utah focused on PCPs from 7 states (Oregon, California, Idaho, Utah, Montana, Wyoming, and Colorado) = 10 million total pts (60% non-urban residents). Arizona focused on PCPs w/in 9 of their 15 counties = ~90% of the state's almost 7 million people.	PCP types, practice settings, pt features, & clinical outcomes	90 attendees participated in teleECHO clinics in the two states; 66 (73%) = PCPs 280 cases of chronic HCV infection were presented @ teleECHO sessions HCV cases mostly among U.S.-born persons, non-Hispanic white, & born during 1945–1965 HCV genotype 1 infection = most common type (62.9%) Pts w/ H/O IVDA = 41.4% (116 of 280)	The application of the Project ECHO model in both states confirmed the value of this care model in expanding the capacity of PCPs primary care clinicians to treat HCV infection. Partnerships w/ specialists will support PCPs to integrate new txs for HCV infection & be vital in improving care access & reducing tx barriers.	Limitations: 1. Inability to eval tx completion amongst some pts R/T either tx completed or awaiting lab results @ time of eval. 2. Unable to explain why tx not started on some pts. 3. Diff. btwn Project ECHO application in each state & pt tx decisions not analyzed. 4. Utah & Arizona already planned their own ECHO Program the yr. before. So, state programs not reflective of those already available. The study did an excellent job of showing that w/ proper training PCPs could safely manage HCV pts.
To describe the impact of using ECHO on PCPs to ↑ pain mgmts. skills (Katzman et al., 2014).	3 diff. methods: Case-based learning, demonstrations, & didactics 3 yr. period; Jan'10 & Dec'12	136 Project ECHO Pain clinic sessions took place involving 763 PCPs across 191 diverse locations w/ 3835	3 methods: (1) Wkly CME surveys; (2) annual clinic data aggregation;	66% self-ID'd as advanced practice or other non-physician health	CME offered via the ECHO Pain program were shown to improve PCP pain mgmt. education. It met not only	Limitations: NO analysis of impact on pt outcomes. Nevertheless, this is an excellent study showing how PCP ↑

Purpose	Design/Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key findings	Author Conclusions	Limitations/Notes
	Wkly educational sessions via tele-health technology	total participation times 2009 @ the University of New Mexico Health Sciences Center	& (3) practice change assessment in clinicians who took part for at least a year.	professional such as NPs. ↑improvements in participants self-reported knowledge, skills, & practice. Also, focus group analyses of 9 participants specifically detailed their practice improvements.	CME objectives but also ↑competence & improved practice by PCPs. Clinicians in non-urban areas can obtain pertinent CME w/o incurring costs & travel time.	competence & practice can be realized via their participation in an ECHO Program.
To learn the effectiveness of a Videoconference-based telehealth system to ↑ HTN mgmt., know-ledge & self-assessed competency amongst PCP (Masi et al. 2012)	Prospective cohort study w/ a comparison group Twelve 1-hr educational sessions PCPs surveyed @ baseline & at once following the curriculum	12 PCPs (9 intervention & 3 controls) 6 FQHCs & 1 large urban healthcare system	PCP HTN mgmt. knowledge & self-assessed competency	All PCPs had pre- and post-participation had varying scores	Use of the ECHO concept had good potential for augmenting the HTN care provision skills of the urban FQHC providers	Limitations: Likelihood of a type II error in control group R/T smaller than the intervention group. Lack of randomization Study did an excellent job of making a case for use ECHO to increase PCP competency.

Notes. Btwn = Between; CME = Continuing medical education; Diff.= Differences; ECHO = Extension for Community Healthcare Outcomes (Project ECHO); = Equal to; HTN = Hypertension; H/O = History of; FQHCs = Federally Qualified Health Centers; IVDA = Intravenous Drug Abuse; Pts = Patients; HCV= Hepatitis-C Virus; NPs = Nurse Practitioners; R/T = Related to; Tx = Treatment; Wkly = weekly W/in = Within